

TREASoURcE

D6.3 Report on funding, public and private investments and building investment pipelines

WP no and title	WP6 Exploitation, replication, and transferable practices
Lead Beneficiary	BT
Responsible Author(s)	Pirkko Eteläaho (BT)
Contributor(s)	Ugur Kaya (VTT) Kaisa Sibelius (FVH) All WP leaders All partners

This document contains case examples on how to promote public and private investments, secure funding, engage stakeholders and build investment pipelines regarding key value chain (KVC) demos and replications carried out and/or planned in TREASoURcE project (Grant Agreement No. 101059491). This deliverable gathers concrete examples about the current landscape of funding opportunities, both from public and private sources, and highlights key areas for future investment by examining successful case studies, innovative financing models and offering insights to drive systemic circular economy solutions. The key objectives of the deliverable are to showcase best practices, replication possibilities, scalability and visibility of circular investment opportunities locally, regionally and beyond.

Project Details			
Project acronym	TREASoURcE	Start / Duration	June 2022 / 48 months
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-01 – Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)'s circular systemic solutions	Grant Agreement No	101059491
Type of Action	Innovation Action (IA)	Coordinator	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
Contact person	Ugur Kaya, ugur.kaya@vt.fi		
Website	https://treasource.eu/		

Deliverable Details			
Deliverable No	6.3		
Deliverable Name	Report on funding, public and private investments and building investment pipelines		
Work Package	WP6 Exploitation, replication, and transferable practices		
Dissemination level	PU - Public	Type	R – Document, report
Due Date (M)	M32 (31.1.2025)	Submission date	29.01.2025
Lead Beneficiary	Business Tampere (BT)	Responsible Author	Pirkko Eteläaho

Deliverable Contributors				
	Name	Organisation	Role / Title	E-mail
Deliverable leader	Pirkko Eteläaho	BT	Exploitation and Business Development Manager	pirkko.etelaaho@businessstampere.com
	Contributing Author(s)	Ugur Kaya	VTT	Project Coordinator
	Kaisa Sibelius	FVH	Replication Manager, WP6 Leader	kaisa.sibelius@forumvirium.fi
	All WP leaders			
	Jan Bakke	Ostfold	Project Manager, WP2 Leader	janbakke@ofk.no
	Riina Kärki	MTK	Project Manager, WP5 Leader	riina.karki@mtk.fi
	Nora Berglund	MTK	Project Manager, WP5 Leader	nora.berglund@mtk.fi
	Aksel Junge Klemsdal	ECO	WP4 co-lead	aksel.junge.klemsdal@eco-stor.no
	Fride Vullum-Bruer	SINTEF	WP4 co-lead	fride.vullum.bruer@sintef.no
	Jacob Hadler-Jacobsen	SINTEF	Researcher	jacob.hadler-jacobsen@sintef.no
	Marion Kade	TARTU	Projects Assistant	marion.kade@tartu.ee
	Anna Gyure-Szamosi	Frstad	Subtask leader 2.2.2	anngyu@fredrikstad.kommune.no
	Mika Kolari	BT	Expert	mika.kolari@businessstampere.com
	All Partners			
Reviewer(s)	Ugur Kaya	VTT	Project Coordinator	ugur.kaya@vtt.fi
	Kaisa Sibelius	FVH	WP6 lead	kaisa.sibelius@forumvirium.fi
Final review and quality approval	Ugur Kaya	VTT	Project Coordinator	ugur.kaya@vtt.fi

Document History			
Date	Version	Name	Changes
24.4.2024	0.1	Draft template	
10.10.2024	0.2	Draft template with case suggestions	Case suggestions added
19.12.2024	0.3	First draft for review	First versions of case descriptions and general text ready
20.1.2025	0.4	Second (final) draft for review	Second (final) draft
29.1.2025	1.0	Final deliverable submitted	Final version

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	9
1. INTRODUCTION.....	10
2. OBJECTIVES AND STRATEGIES	11
3. EXAMPLES OF FUNDING AND FINANCING POSSIBILITIES TO BOOST CIRCULAR ECONOMY INVESTMENTS.....	12
3.1. Public funding sources.....	12
3.2. Private funding sources.....	16
3.3. Innovative financing models.....	16
3.4. Funding guides and platforms.....	17
4. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT DEMOS (SE-DEMOS) AND REPLICATIONS, CASE EXAMPLES	18
4.1. Battery investments for public and private companies.....	18
4.1.1. Background	18
4.1.2. Stakeholder engagement workshop.....	18
4.1.3. Replication opportunities.....	19
4.1.4. Joint procurement in battery storage systems	22
4.2. Rentable recycling trailer for events and educational program on recycling.....	22
4.2.1. Background	22
4.2.2. Preparations	22
4.2.3. Outcome and concept	23
4.2.4. Development of educational concept and rental of trailer.....	23
4.2.5. Financing and costs	24
4.3. Fix and Repair Workshops: Learnings from Norway and Estonia.....	24
4.3.1. Fix and Repair Workshops in Fredrikstad.....	25
4.3.2. Paranduskelder in Tartu.....	27
4.4. ELiCo concept – The Recycling Master online course.....	29
4.4.1. The background.....	29
4.4.2. Preparation	29
4.4.3. The focus groups.....	30
4.4.4. Desired requirements	30
4.4.5. Replicability and localisation	30
4.4.6. Financing options for the course.....	31
5. KEY VALUE CHAIN DEMONSTRATIONS (KVC-DEMOS) AND REPLICATIONS, CASE EXAMPLES	34
5.1. Plastics	34
5.1.1. Rigid plastics collection	34
5.1.2. Chemical recycling of plastics.....	36
5.1.3. Circulated fluidized bed.....	42

5.1.4. MODIX technology pilot.....	43
5.2. EV batteries.....	43
5.2.1. Battery room and investment	43
5.2.2. Three demo sites.....	44
5.2.3. Optimization of BESS utilization.....	46
5.3. Biobased side streams.....	50
5.3.1. Marketplace for biobased side and waste streams – KiertoaSuomesta.fi..	50
5.3.2. Local bioeconomy system models development in Tampere region.....	52
5.4. Cross-cutting: The role of sustainability assessments in building investment pipelines for circular economy projects	54
5.4.1. Public funding	54
5.4.2. Private funding.....	54
5.4.3. Sustainability assessment framework for informing investments	55
5.4.4. Engaging stakeholders with the assessment results	55
5.4.5. A novel sustainability and circularity assessment framework developed in the TREASoURcE project.....	56
6. CONCLUSIONS AND SUMMARY	56
7. REFERENCES.....	57

Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
A/C	Air Conditioning
BaaS	Battery as a Service
BESS	Battery Stationary Energy Storage
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
BT	Business Tampere
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CE	Circular Economy
CF	Cohesion Fund
CLIC	CLIC Innovation Ltd
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
D	Deliverable Report
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
ECO	Ecostor
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIP-AGRI	European Agriculture and Innovation Network
EIS	Enterprise Estonia
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows)
ELiCo	Enlightened Consumer
ELY	Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment
EORI	Economic Operators Registration and Identification
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESG	Environmental, Social, Governance
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ESF+	European Social Fund Plus
ETAg	Estonian Research Council
EV	Electric Vehicle
eta_c	Charging Efficiency
eta_d	Discharging Efficiency
Frstad	Fredrikstad kommune
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	GreenDelta GmbH
HCl	Hydrochloric Acid
HK-dir	Directorate for Higher Education and Skills

IEC	International Electrotechnical Committee
JICE	Joint Initiative on Circular Economy
JTF	Just Transition Fund
KIK	Environmental Investment Centre
KVC	Key Value Chain
KVC-DEMO	Key Value Chain Demonstration
LAG	Local Action Group
Li-Ion	Lithium Ion
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessments
MAC	Media Access Control
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
MODIX	Modular Shredder-Mixer-Extruder
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
NIR	Near Infrared
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OST	Østfold fylkeskommune
P_low	Spot Price When Charging
P_profit	Profit For One Charge Discharge Cycle For a BESS
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PF	Polyfuels Group AB (Previously known as Green Ideas Group GIG)
PP	Polypropylene
PPP	Public-Private Partnerships
PRIA	Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board
PS	Polystyrene
PVC	Polyvinylchloride
R	The Ratio Between the Price When Charging and the Price When Discharging
R&D	Research and Development
RTK	State Shared Service Center Estonia
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
SE	Stakeholder Engagement
SE-DEMO	Stakeholder Engagement Demonstration
SINTEF	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Energy
TAMK	Tampere University of Applied Sciences
TalTech	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

VAT	Value Added Tax
VC	Venture Capital
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd

Executive Summary

The deliverable D6.3 “Report on funding, public and private investments and building investment pipelines” is a document giving insights on promoting investments in circular economy by showcasing best practices, innovative financing models, and successful case studies developed, demonstrated and replicated in Horizon-Europe funded TREASoURcE. The report’s primary objectives are to enhance the visibility of successful case studies and related funding / investment opportunities, and by strengthening stakeholder engagement building impactful investment pipelines. By leveraging diverse funding sources, including EU programs, national and regional grants, venture capital, private equity, and green bonds, the report provides an outlook on possibilities for both public and private investments. It emphasizes the importance of replication and scalability, offering concrete examples and guidelines to replicate successful projects in different regions. The report also highlights the critical role of life cycle assessments (LCA) in demonstrating the environmental, social, and economic benefits of circular economy projects, thereby attracting both public and private funding.

In addition to identifying available funding sources, the report also touches upon innovative financing models such as public-private partnerships (PPPs), crowdfunding, and investment readiness programs. These models are crucial for attracting a diverse range of investors and ensuring the financial sustainability of circular economy initiatives. The report also underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement through workshops, seminars, and public outreach activities. By fostering collaboration among all key stakeholders, strong networks and joint initiatives for supporting investments in systemic circular economy solutions can be achieved.

The report includes successful case studies carried out in TREASoURcE, such as battery storage solutions, innovative circular economy solutions for plastics, versatile biobased side stream utilization and stakeholder engagement methods. These case studies provide practical insights into the funding strategies and replication potential of various circular economy solutions. By sharing these examples, the report aims to inspire other regions and stakeholders to adopt similar practices, thereby promoting circular economy solution implementation on a larger scale. D6.3 serves as a resource for stakeholders looking to invest in circular economy initiatives offering practical insights, strategic guidance, and concrete examples to implement investments and build resilient investment pipelines.

1. INTRODUCTION

The deliverable D6.3 “Report on funding, public and private investments and building investment pipelines” collects examples of systemic circular economy solutions developed in TREASoURcE and how the solutions could be promoted through public and private investments. This deliverable focuses on gathering concrete examples of funding opportunities from both public and private sources, highlighting key areas for future investment by examining successful case studies and innovative financing models. The report aims to provide stakeholders with practical insights and strategic guidance to secure funding, engage stakeholders, and build investment pipelines for key value chain (KVC) demonstrations and replications. By showcasing best practices, replication possibilities, and scalability, the report seeks to enhance the visibility of circular investment opportunities locally, regionally, and beyond. The ultimate goal is to support the transition to a circular economy by fostering sustainable investments and building resilient investment pipelines.

The report touches upon a diverse range of funding sources, including European Union programs, national and regional grants, venture capital, private equity, and green bonds. Furthermore, the report highlights the importance of stakeholder engagement in building investment pipelines. The report also underscores the critical role of life cycle assessments (LCA) in demonstrating the environmental, social, and economic benefits of circular economy projects. By providing transparent and quantitative metrics, these assessments help attract both public and private funding.

The report consists of case studies of successful development work, demos and replications carried out and / or planned in TREASoURcE, offering practical insights and guidelines for replication and scalability of systemic CE solutions related to plastics, EV batteries and bio-based side streams in wide stakeholder collaboration through different funding and financing routes and investment planning.

2. OBJECTIVES AND STRATEGIES

The objectives of D6.3 are aimed at promoting public and private investments in systemic CE solutions related to plastics, EV batteries and bio-based side streams. It provides examples of key value chain (KVC) and stakeholder engagement (SE) demonstrations and replications within the TREASoURcE project with special aspects from the funding landscape and investment pipeline building.

The objectives of the deliverable can be summarized as following:

1. **Showcase Best Practices:** Highlight successful case studies and innovative financing models to demonstrate effective strategies for securing investments in CE demos and / or replications that have been carried out or planned in Horizon TREASoURcE.
2. **Promote Replication and Scalability:** Provide concrete examples and guidelines to replicate successful CE solutions in different regions, ensuring scalability and broader impact of the solutions.
3. **Enhance Visibility of Investment Opportunities:** Increase awareness of CE investment opportunities at local, regional, and international levels.
4. **Engage Stakeholders:** Foster collaboration among public and private stakeholders to build efficient investment pipelines and secure funding for CE initiatives.

The key focus areas of the D6.3 include exploration of available public funding sources such as EU programs, national and regional grants, and other public funding opportunities. It also provides insights into private funding sources, including venture capital, private equity, impact investments, and corporate sustainability programs. The report also touches on other innovative models to support circular economy investments. It includes in-depth case studies of specific demos and / or replications, such as battery storage solutions, recycling trailers, and biogas plants, emphasizing their funding strategies and replication potential. Horizontally, the report presents frameworks for assessing the sustainability and circularity of the solutions to support investment decisions, ensuring that investments are aligned with environmental, social, and economic goals.

D6.3 serves as an influential resource for regions and stakeholders looking to invest in circular economy initiatives - offering practical insights, strategic guidance, and concrete examples on how to promote CE investments and build resilient investment pipelines.

3. EXAMPLES OF FUNDING AND FINANCING POSSIBILITIES TO BOOST CIRCULAR ECONOMY INVESTMENTS

This Chapter summarizes some examples of available funding sources on EU, national and regional levels for CE-related development and implementation initiatives, covering both public and private sources as well as some innovative financing solutions.

3.1. Public funding sources

Some examples of available public funding sources for CE solutions on EU, national and local levels are listed below:

- **European Union programs, funds, loans, i.e.**
 - **Horizon Europe:** This EU research and innovation program supports projects that contribute to the circular economy through substantial funding and collaborative opportunities (Horizon Europe, 2024).
 - **LIFE Programme:** This EU funding instrument focuses on environmental and climate action, including circular economy projects (LIFE Programme, 2024).
 - **Interreg Europe:** funds projects that promote regional development and cooperation across Europe (Interreg Europe, 2024).
 - **European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF):** These funds, such as European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) (European Regional Development Fund, 2024), Cohesion Fund (CF) (Cohesion Fund, 2024), European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) (European Social Fund Plus, 2024) and European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) (European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, 2024) support various circular economy projects, including waste management, resource efficiency, and green jobs (European Structural and Investment Funds, 2024).
 - **Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE):** This initiative involves several national promotional banks and institutions, including the European Investment Bank (EIB) (European Investment Bank, 2024), providing loans, equity investments, guarantees, and advisory services (Joint Initiative on Circular Economy, 2024).

- **EIB and the Circular City Centre C3** – Circular City Centre C3 (Circular City Centre C3, 2021) is a competence and resource centre within EIB, which supports EU cities in their circular economy transition. It is a joint initiative between the EIB and the European Commission.
 - **European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT):** investment funds cover different areas and can support start-ups and even new ideas that lead to start-ups. Areas cover Climate-KIC, Digital, Food, Health, InnoEnergy, Manufacturing, Raw Materials, Urban Mobility, and Culture & Creativity (European Institute of Innovation & Technology, 2024).
 - **Green Transition Partnerships:** For instance, during the COP29 conference in November 2024, EU Cohesion Policy 83 M€ euro call on green transition partnerships was presented (Green Transition Partnerships, 2024).
- **National and Regional Agencies**

National Agencies

- **Finland, i.e.:**
 - **Business Finland** – Business Finland offers funding opportunities and invest in / export support for Finnish companies, helping them grow and succeed globally, develop solutions for the future and renew their business operations. Business Finland promotes collaboration between companies and research groups, so that new international business ecosystems can be formed (Business Finland, 2024).
 - **Finnvera** – Finnvera is a a state-owned specialised financing company that strengthens the operating potential and competitiveness of Finnish enterprises by offering loans, domestic guarantees, export credit guarantees, and other services associated with the financing of exports (Finnvera, 2024).
 - **Tesi** (Finnish Industry Investment Ltd) is a state-owned, market-driven investment company that invests in venture capital and private equity funds and directly in sustainable Finnish startup, growth and industrial companies (Tesi, 2024).
 - **Research Council of Finland** - The Research Council of Finland is a government agency within the administrative branch of the Finnish Ministry of Education, Science and Culture. It is an expert organisation in science and

research, funding high-quality scientific research, providing expertise in science and science policy and strengthening the position of science and research. (Research Council of Finland, 2024).

- **The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra** – Sitra is a fund directly accountable to the Finnish Parliament, and their decision-making processes are tied to parliamentary systems. Sitra’s mission is to promote the well-being of Finland and accelerate economic growth within the limits of nature’s carrying capacity. (The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra, 2024).
 - **Ministries** such as Ministry of Economic Affairs and Development (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Development, 2024), Ministry of the Environment (Ministry of Environment, 2024) and Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2024) are funding various circular economy related projects.
 - **Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY Centres)** – The Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY Centres) are responsible for the regional implementation and development tasks of the central government. Finland has a total of 15 ELY Centres, which are tasked with promoting regional competitiveness, well-being and sustainable development and curbing climate change. (Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment, 2024).
- **Estonia, i.e.:**
- **Environmental Investment Centre (KIK)** – The Environmental Investment Centre is a financial institution, mediating state budget funds (revenues from environmental charges), EU funds, funds from foreign aid programmes and the Green Investment Scheme as well as granting loans for the implementation of environmental projects. KIK belongs to the administration area of the Ministry of the Climate. (Environmental Investment Centre, 2024).
 - **Enterprise Estonia (EIS)** – Enterprise Estonia is a public sector organization with the goals of increasing Estonia’s international competitiveness, developing entrepreneurship, and improving the living environment. (Enterprise Estonia, 2024) .

- **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)** – The ERDF supports regional development, innovation, research and development activities, and the growth of small enterprises. In Estonia, the distribution of grants from this fund is coordinated by the State Shared Service Center (RTK) (RTK, 2025).
 - **Estonian Research Council (ETAg)** – ETAg funds research and development activities, including regional research projects and international cooperation programs (ETAg, 2025).
 - **Norway, i.e.:**
 - **Research Council of Norway** – The Research Council of Norway’s aim is to promote a society where research is created, used and shared, and thus contributes to restructuring and enhanced sustainability (Research Council of Norway, 2024).
 - **Innovation Norway** – Innovation Norway helps Norwegian companies to grow sustainably and increase exports by providing access to competence, capital and networks, including green investment grants for selected districts (Innovation Norway, 2024).
 - **Enova** – Enova is owned by the Ministry of Climate and Environment, and it contributes to a faster transition to a low-emission society by funding pilots and providing partial funding for investments supporting sustainable solutions (Enova, 2024).
- Regional Development Funds such as Council of Tampere Region (Council of Tampere Region, 2024) and Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council (Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council, 2024) in Finland, Regionale Forskningsfond (Regionale Forskningsfond, 2024) in Norway, Tallinn and Tartu city Government Grants in Estonia (Tallinn City Government Grants, 2025) (Tartu City Government Grants, 2025).
- National aids such as energy and investment aid from the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Development, (Energy and Investment Aid, 2024) and energy aid (Energy Aid, 2024) from Business Finland in Finland, Enova (Enova, 2024) and Bionova (Bionova, 2024) funding of climate measures within agricultural, forestry and aquaculture businesses in Norway and Estonian Ministry of the Climate Grants (through Environmental Investment Centre) (Environmental Investment Centre, 2024), Energy Efficiency Aid from KredEx (KredEx, 2025), Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board (PRIA) (PRIA, 2025) in Estonia.

3.2. Private funding sources

- **Venture Capital, Private Equity and Impact Investments:** Firms that invest in innovative startups and companies developing circular economy solutions. The investments help scale up new technologies and business models generating also social and environmental impact alongside financial returns. For example, Taaleri (Taaleri, 2024) and Korona Invest (Korona Invest, 2024) in Finland.
- **Green Bonds:** Issued by corporations, municipalities, and financial institutions to raise capital specifically for projects with environmental benefits, including circular economy initiatives. For example, Fingrid (Fingrid, 2017) in Finland.
- **Corporate Sustainability Programs and Green Deals:** Many large corporations have dedicated funds and programs to support circular economy projects within their supply chains and operations and commitments to i.e. Green Deals. Examples of companies that have committed to the national Circular Economy Green Deal in Finland include i.e. Boreal, Orhex, Metsä Group, GRK and Skanska (CE Green Deal Commitments, 2024).
- **Industry partnerships** – programs that foster business and R&D collaboration within industrial players and/or academia, for instance Valmet's Beyond Circularity Program (Beyond Circularity, 2022) and Kiilto's Superhealthy Buildings Ecosystem (Superhealthy Buildings Ecosystem, 2024) in Finland
- **Foundations** – many foundations fund climate actions and circular economy related activities, such as the Baltic Sea Action Group (Baltic Sea Action Group, 2024)

3.3. Innovative financing models

- **Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)** – public-private partnerships can promote circular economy solutions and sustainability in many ways, as examples ongoing work of EIT InnoEnergy (EIT InnoEnergy, 2024) and one of the pioneers in Finland, Smart and Clean Foundation that was operating in 2016-2021 (Smart and Clean, 2016).
- **Crowdfunding** – crowdfunding is a method of raising small amounts of money from a large number of stakeholders. This approach allows entrepreneurs, artists, and organizations to gather financial support from a broad audience, often in exchange for rewards, early access to products, or simply the satisfaction of supporting. It leverages platforms like Innovestor (Innovestor, 2024), Kickstarter (Kickstarter, 2024) and Indiegogo (Indiegogo, 2024).
- **Investment Readiness Programs** - the aim of these programs is to support innovators at various stages of their fundraising journey, whether they are just starting or already mature to bring their projects to market. The programmes aim to enhance the investor readiness of innovators, providing them with the necessary tools and knowledge to attract investment and scale their ventures. One example of this kind of program is EIC Investor

Readiness and Outreach Programme (EIC Investor Readiness and Outreach Programme, 2024).

3.4. Funding guides and platforms

On EU-level, there are several portals and platforms that help in navigating the funding landscape, so it is good to explore their possibilities and utilize them actively. Just to mention a few examples:

- **Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)** – CCRI network provides insights and shares information from the pilot and fellow cities and regions along with a good number of CCRI projects (Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, 2024).
- **Circular City Funding Guide** – A comprehensive guide on finding suitable funding routes to promote CE solutions in urban context. Through the platform one may access information, for instance, on alternative funding sources such as crowd funding, leasing, green bonds, social impact bonds, equities, grants and subsidies, guarantees and debts (Circular City Funding Guide, 2024).
- **The Invest EU Portal** – the umbrella portal that brings together investors and project promoters, allowing visibility to projects from the EU + Norway & Iceland (InvestEU, 2024).
- **JASPERS** – provides free assistance to regional and local authorities such as project appraisal support for the beneficiaries (JASPERS, 2024).
- **European City Facility** – provides fast-track access to a fixed-grant of 60.000 EUR to develop project concepts (e.g. feasibility studies, legal analysis etc) which can later turn into full project proposals. (European City Facility, 2024).
- **Smart Cities Marketplace** (Smart Cities Marketplace, 2024) and **Scalable Cities** (Scalable Cities, 2024) – both offer a plethora of information and guidance to cities of all sizes.
- **Urbact** – its networks, policy tools and catalogue of Good Practices might be useful for circular economy or cross-cutting topics (Urbact, 2024).
- **FiCompass** – an umbrella portal for funding instruments under shared EU management such as the ERDF and ESF. This can be useful for regions and for anybody interested in understand how they work. You can see how much of the funding your country has used and on which priority topics (FiCompass, 2024).

4. Stakeholder engagement demos (SE-demos) and replications, case examples

4.1. Battery investments for public and private companies

4.1.1. Background

For investment and procurement of battery stationary energy storage (BESS) there are a number of considerations that needs to be made during planning, procurement, installation and operation. Previous work in TREASoURcE D1.4 State-of-the-art analysis of technologies, circular business models and ecodesign practices for plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based side and waste streams (TREASoURcE, D1.4 State-of-the-art analysis of technologies, circular business models and ecodesign practices for plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based side and waste streams, 2023), D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains (TREASoURcE, D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains, 2024) and D4.1 Existing and upcoming challenges for extending electric vehicle battery lifetime (TREASoURcE, D4.1 Existing and upcoming challenges for extending electric vehicle battery lifetime, 2023)) have done thorough mapping of the existing legislative landscape for batteries. The main document governing batteries in the EU is the Battery Regulation, which entered into force in August 2023 (EU Battery Regulation, 2023) . This regulation defines requirements concerning the whole value chain from raw materials to recycling. However, one main topic which is not covered in the Battery Regulation is the installation of batteries and safety related to installation, operation and use of large BESS. Installation is covered for new batteries, and partially for 2nd life batteries, in the IEC (International Electrotechnical Committee) standards, which in many countries are translated into national standards. Still, there are no European or national standards in any of the countries participating in TREASoURcE, defining standards or regulations for battery rooms and safe operation of BESS. This was identified as one of the major challenges for accelerated uptake of both first life and 2nd life BESS. However, other barriers also exist, and it is important to understand the market needs and knowledge gaps to better target the important areas for expanding the BESS market.

4.1.2. Stakeholder engagement workshop

As part of deliverable D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains (TREASoURcE, D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains, 2024) a stakeholder engagement workshop was organized in Fredrikstad. The workshop was organized as a collaboration between SINTEF and Fredrikstad and focused on installation of solar panels and BESS. Local industry was invited to present their solutions in addition to presentations from TREASoURcE partners. The second part of the

day included group work where the different partners worked on identifying both opportunities and barriers related to installation of BESS in buildings and on industry sites.

Some of the challenges and opportunities identified during the group work included:

- Establish incentives through support for investments in BESS. This could for example be done through Enova in Norway.
- Lack of knowledge and information hinders accelerated uptake of BESS. Increased knowledge through media and educate both the general public and industry sector.
- Safety of BESS installations in buildings is a big issue. Lack of information and knowledge amongst engineers may make planning and installation of BESS much more costly than necessary. Establishing standard procedures for safety assessments and national or European standards for battery room requirements would simplify the processes with procurement, installation and operation of BESS.
- Most people do not see the full potential of BESS. The main perception is that BESS can be used for storing excess energy from solar panels or for peak shaving and load shifting. Other services such as frequency regulation and other similar grid services are not well known. Using a battery for more than one specific purpose would greatly reduce the pay-back time for the BESS.
- Not sufficient knowledge about how 2nd life batteries perform with respect to new batteries. Uncertainties related to lifetime and safety reduce the likelihood of companies investing in 2nd life BESS.

4.1.3. Replication opportunities

Similar workshops and discussions as that described above can be done with other stakeholder groups. Also, spreading the knowledge gained through the work in TREASoURcE through stakeholder engagement workshops, seminars or other public outreach can contribute to greatly enhance the general knowledge about BESS installations for both 1st life and 2nd life batteries. Other stakeholder groups that are important to reach out to include (but is not limited to):

- Fire engineers and consultants with knowledge within battery systems
- Battery experts, including battery systems, battery cells and electronic components
- Energy management system and communication system providers.
- Fire rescue services and fire brigade

In replication, the following requirements should be considered based on Lempäälä-house learnings:

Initial battery room requirements:

- **Floor capability to hold a lot of weight:** In the study case one module weights over 700 kg. Two modules were installed.
- **Physical dimensions:** In the study case the module's footprint was ~80 cm x 120 cm. Transportation pallet is 2 m height. In addition to space in the room, the doorway to the room needs to be checked.
- **Room temperature and ventilation:** In the study case the room temperature should be between 10 and 30°C; ideally 15-20°C. Humidity must be <95%, non-condensing. As the installation will produce heat, ventilation or preferably A/C (air conditioning) is necessary. Battery system's peak heat production is around 2-2.5 kW. Total heat produced during a day: in the range of 5-8 kWh with heavy load on the system.
- **Electrical connections:** Grid connection and protection equipment needed. Internet connection. The facility should be approved as grid electricity producer/consumer by the local electricity grid.
- **Room access:** People getting access to the room should be controlled.

Process steps:

Based on the study case the following process steps are needed for the successful installation process.

1. Identification of proper room for the system. Requirements for the pilot case shown in initial room requirements (described above).
2. Information about the building power consumption and production to be sent to the battery manufacturer to calculate optimal size of the BESS (capacity and power) and potential benefits and use cases for the system.
3. In municipality-owned buildings an office holder decision for the project is needed. An office holder decision needs to be publicly available for 30 days.
4. Local fire department check for the suitability of the room and possible recommendations. Fire load of the system impacts on the requirements.
5. Specifying the gaps between the room facilities and battery manufacturer's specification and safety authority guidance. In the study case the following were needed:
 - a. Fire suppression system: The local fire department recommended aerosol-based fire suppression system.

- b. Ventilation system: Air-to-air heat pump selected. Possibilities were liquid cooling system, but the layout of the room restricted the option: Liquid cannot be on the top of electrical connections.
 - c. Electrical cabinets for the ventilation and the fire suppression system.
 - d. Integration of the battery system and auxiliary devices into building automation system: In the study case also power meters were added to the system for monitoring purposes.
 - e. Grid connection and protection devices.
6. A permit of local grid company needed if the battery is connected to the electricity grid. Inverter rated power impacts to the requirements for the grid connection.
7. Building permit needed because the storage room was changed into the electrical room.
8. The pilot battery system needs to have access to the Internet. In the study case information about the location of the battery manufacturer's server, MAC (Media Access Control) address and functional schematic needed for the local network provider.
9. Installation of the battery system might impact building insurance. In the study case, the insurance company needed information about the part number, original equipment manufacturer and brand of the batteries as well as the electrical inspection minutes for the system.
10. If the battery is delivered outside EU, it needs to pass the customs declaration. Receiving organisation, in this case Finnish organisation, is needed. Customs needs EORI-number (Economic Operators Registration and Identification -number) from the organisation. Freight forwarder needs power of attorney document for customs by the receiver. If the sender has EUR.1 – certificate there is not any cost for the receiver (EORI Number Registration Service, 2024).
11. Installations
 - a. Installation and testing of auxiliary systems have to be ready before the battery installation.
 - b. Installation of the battery system to the grid and to the solar panel system. Person doing the electrical work in Finland needs to be qualified (Tukes - Electrical Works in Finland, 2024).
 - c. Building automation tests after the battery is connected to the grid.
 - d. Fire suppression system turned on when all assembly work is finalized in the room. In the meanwhile, the battery can be used only when somebody is present in the room.
12. Guidance to people allowed access to the battery room or E-stop button. Instructions how to act in a case of safety hazard given.
13. After commissioning

- Certified inspector needs to inspect the system within 6 months (Tukes - Electrical Works in Finland, 2024). Document will be sent to insurance company and fire authority.
- Fire department inspection for the system and the room.

4.1.4. Joint procurement in battery storage systems

One opportunity to promote the replication of results could be through joint procurements by municipalities and operators. A model that describes how a public entity could jointly procure energy storage systems. This could particularly facilitate the market entry of 2nd life batteries. By using a joint procurement model, planning and preparation can be better focused, and the implementation itself can be done more quickly. At the same time, the final (2nd life) battery storage cost is lower because it is a scalable and modular solution.

The entire supply chain, from manufacturing to installation, operation, maintenance, and recycling, would be more carefully planned, but the final solution would be cheaper yet still more profitable for each lifecycle stage operator.

A joint procurement model can include requirements for social, environmental, and economic sustainability, as well as criteria affecting recyclability, maintenance, and use. One model for battery procurement in TREASoURcE project is to purchase batteries in series of ten. The Lempäälä-house pilot also shows that the first implementation is always the most expensive, but if ten similar ones are made, the last one would be the cheapest. One motivation for joint procurements would be price equalization, where prices are averaged at the end of the procurement series, allowing the first operator to receive a refund. Another advantage is scheduling, where timelines can be adjusted within the ordered series of batteries.

4.2. Rentable recycling trailer for events and educational program on recycling

4.2.1. Background

Recycling solutions at events often have quite limited sets of waste fractions and are designed for stationary events only. The aim of producing and developing a recycling trailer was to provide a full-scale waste handling solution for mobile events to reduce the residual waste and significantly increase the CE practice of the Tour of Scandinavia women's cycling race.

4.2.2. Preparations

The development of the trailer was done in co-operation between County of Østfold, the event organizer and its volunteers and a local trailer business which is responsible for the production and the renting of

the trailer. The third-party-based environmental certification scheme, Eco-lighthouse, guided the background mapping of practices and relevant environmental issues and reporting which resulted in the decision to come up with a mobile waste sorting solution. The county has a role as a supporter of regional events and festivals and acted as a facilitator in the process to start the event's journey towards environmental certification. The event organizers and volunteers contributed with practical advice and contributions on necessary functions and designs to make the trailer easy to use. The recycling trailer was first demonstrated at local events in connection with the 2023 Ladies Tour of Scandinavia and has since been rented to a significant number of other events.

4.2.3. Outcome and concept

The outcome of the SE-demo is a highly visible rentable multi-fraction waste sorting and recycling solution for event organizers which aims to 1) significantly increase recycling rates of both plastic and bio-waste at events and 2) engage and educate citizens, especially children and their families, on how to sort and recycle their waste. The recycling trailer contains waste sorting solutions for 6 different waste fractions and can be rented and used at both stationary and mobile events.

The renting of the trailer is currently handled by the local trailer company which developed and built the prototype. To use the recycling trailer concept most efficiently it is vital that the organization of the rental concept is handled by an actor which has an organization to efficiently handle frequent rentals.

The recycling trailer is most efficiently exploited when combined with an educational or edutainment show utilizing pictograms, colourful objects (rubber and plastic balls) and a waste sorting relay to creatively engage children and their families on recognizing different waste types and how to sort them correctly. This is a commercial concept offered by and executed by well-known media profiles, which for many events will require external sponsoring or funding to be included.

4.2.4. Development of educational concept and rental of trailer

The recycling trailer has a great potential as an educational tool also outside of events as a part of CE training and actions on recycling and waste sorting, understanding different kinds of materials and their properties. Public utilities, like science and education centres, can co-operate with waste management companies on developing age-specific CE-training materials on recycling and waste sorting, where the science and education centre manages the practicalities surrounding the trailer. This can be combined with a function of renting the trailer for events and festivals, thereby ensuring a more optimized and efficient utilization of the trailer.

4.2.5. Financing and costs

The development costs for the recycling trailer was around 30 000 Euro. The development of the trailer was co-funded by regional sports' and cultural funds for event management. The recycling trailer concept can however easily be adapted and tailored for other countries and ordered by local vendors to reduce investment costs. The cost for purchasing a localized version of the trailer is in Norway ca. 21-22 000 Euros and a localized version can be ordered in other countries.

Financing options Norway:

Public funding and grants:

Financing options for the recycling trailer include regional public funds (county level) for sport and culture and regional climate action funds. (Ostfold, 2025)

Foundations:

Gjensidigestiftelsen:

Supports projects that benefit society, particularly those focused on education and the environment. (Gjensidigestiftelsen, 2024).

Sparebankstiftelsen:

Foundation of savings bank supports actions that benefit community building (Sparebankstiftelsen, 2024).

Financing options Estonia:

Environmental Investment Centre (KIK):

Provides grants for projects related to environmental protection, sustainability, and education (Environmental Investment Centre, 2024).

4.3. Fix and Repair Workshops: Learnings from Norway and Estonia

This section provides an overview of fix and repair workshop cases in Fredrikstad (Norway) and Tartu (Estonia). While the Norwegian experience demonstrates how to highlight the importance of reuse and sustainability during cultural events, the case of *Paranduskelder* in Estonia shows how the educational experience of repairing own items can be brought to local community. Each subsection also provides a glimpse into financial perspectives and funding opportunities when it comes to replicating these practices in other countries.

4.3.1. Fix and Repair Workshops in Fredrikstad

Culture Night is a yearly cultural event in Fredrikstad when people can experience concerts, theatre, film screenings exhibitions, cultural walks, dance and much more from both professionals and amateurs - all in one evening, all around in the city. It usually takes place in the beginning of autumn and attracts a lot of city residents. During autumn 2024 the city of Fredrikstad put a lot of emphasis on sustainability and reuse. Several fixing and repair workshops were organised during the Culture Night to highlight the importance of reuse and repurposing, so that all residents would become aware of it. There were several locations where citizens could get repaired cloth, electronic devices, shoes, bags and jewellery free of charge (Case Fredrikstad | Fix and Repair Workshops in “Culture Night” Event, 2024).

Several vocational schools were participating in the event, including students studying repair of electrical infrastructure, sewing, shoemaking and goldsmithing. In addition to the free of charge repair services that were provided by the students, a professional fixing workshop, REbyME, was set up, where people were taught how to repair their clothes or other textiles themselves making the workshop an educational experience rather than a purely service-oriented one. This focus on interactive learning empowered participants by giving them the tools to continue repairing items on their own in the future.

To guarantee the workshops reached their objectives, the focus was placed on both the practical and educational aspects of sustainability. *Ungt Entreprenørskap* (Young Entrepreneurship) was an important partner in that. *Ungt Entreprenørskap* is a non-profit, nationwide organization that, together with the education system, companies and other actors, works to develop children and young people's creativity and entrepreneurial skills. Under the guidance of this NGO, students can set up their own student-led companies and carry out fixing services through these companies fostering a real-world business environment where they could showcase their abilities and learn about customer service, pricing, and time management (Young Entrepreneurship, 2024).

The hands-on nature of the workshops, combined with the opportunity to learn repair skills from professionals, ensured that the event would leave a lasting impact on the community. Overall, the event proved to be a success: there were locations where people were queuing up before opening with products waiting to be repaired. This suggests that the workshops could benefit from increased capacity in the future. Another piece of feedback involved expanding the types of items that could be repaired, with several participants asking for the inclusion of bicycle repair or furniture repurposing. Based on the feedback and outcomes, there is clear potential for developing a more regular schedule for repair workshops, possibly quarterly or even bimonthly. It could be useful to organize the workshops same time at the same location, so the residents of Fredrikstad could get used to it. This would also help in the marketing of the event.

The fix and repair workshops should also be continued at big festivals, since large events get a lot of publicity and attract large crowds. The fix and repair activities attracted a lot of national media attention and hence, are anticipated to have good potential in future. For future development, it would be beneficial to explore sustainable funding models to ensure the workshops can continue to run free of charge or at a minimal cost. Cooperation with the students is essential in that.

Here are three most important factors to keep in mind when establishing something similar (How to Set up a Fix and Repair Workshop in a Cultural Event, 2024):

- **Market research**

Study and analyse the already existing repair services, platforms and actors. It is important to collaborate with stakeholders that have the same focus and get as much information as possible before starting your initiative.

- **Cooperation**

Broad collaboration is essential across all market stakeholders and at multiple societal levels to organize repair workshops and to inspire people towards reuse. This joint effort ensures that repair initiatives are well-supported, making reuse accessible and appealing, and ultimately fostering a culture where people feel motivated to prioritize sustainable choices and minimize waste. Broad collaboration strengthens networks, builds trust, and increases awareness, making it easier to coordinate efforts and achieve lasting impact. The cooperation with Young Entrepreneurship enabled students to practice entrepreneurial skills by providing repair services under their student-run companies, fostering a real-world business environment where they could showcase their abilities and learn about customer service, pricing, and time management.

- **Budgeting**

Explore sustainable funding models to ensure the workshops can be free of charge or at a minimal cost. To involve students from vocational schools to repair things is economically sustainable.

Due to cooperation with vocational schools and free municipal locations (the event took place in the main library in Fredrikstad) there were no investment costs. Repair tools and equipment were also delivered by the students from the school. Going beyond one-time event and starting regular fix and repair workshops would imply that future investments would likely be directed towards materials and consumables, like threads, electronic components, and repair parts. Also, there might be costs associated with the training for volunteers to improve their repair skills in case volunteers will be involved in addition to students.

The primary operational costs will include:

1. **Hourly wages for students:** for future events, student participants will charge hourly rates via their student-owned companies. Approximate costs are depending on local regulations and the number of students involved.
2. **Materials for repairs:** consistent restocking of necessary repair materials (threads, screws, adhesives) is needed to support regular workshops.
3. **Venue costs (if applicable):** If future events are not held in a free public space, venue rental fees must be budgeted as well. The city of Fredrikstad will continue cooperation with the Main Library in Fredrikstad, hence, not budget would be needed for venue costs.

Here are a few tips regarding funding opportunities:

- **Public Funding:** Partnerships with municipalities and public schools could cover venue costs and student wages, ensuring accessibility and supporting community engagement.

- **Private Sponsorships:** Contributions from local businesses or repair-focused brands can further offset costs, possibly covering tools and supplies or sponsoring specific workshops in exchange for visibility.
- **Grants and Sustainability Funds:** Many organizations and government programs provide sustainability-focused funding, which aligns well with the goals of promoting reuse and repair.

For regular, sustainable fix and repair workshops, a mix of public support, possible grant applications, and private partnerships (e.g., with REbyME) would ensure both financial stability and resource availability.

4.3.2. Paranduskelder in Tartu

Paranduskelder (Paranduskelder, 2024) (meaning Repair Basement in Estonian) operates as a repair workshop located in the south of Estonia, the city of Tartu. Its concept is simple yet powerful: extend the life of consumer goods through repair, education, and community engagement. *Paranduskelder* serves as a hub where anyone can walk in with a broken item, whether it's clothing, electronics, or bicycles, and receive assistance from skilled craftsmen. The focus here is on repair, upcycling and do-it-yourself activities, encouraging change within people's habits and mindset towards repairing.

Paranduskelder is owned by the non-governmental organization that has been organizing Repair Cafes (Repair Cafes, 2017) since 2017 in various places around Estonia. In November 2019 they opened their own workshop in the basement of an old factory complex and called it *Paranduskelder*. Since then, various workshops, events and lectures connected to sustainable lifestyle have been organized and they have been working towards building a resilient community. The community includes professionally skilled craftsmen, engineers, architects, creatives, educators and artists. NGO is funded yearly by the municipality of Tartu.

Additionally, *Paranduskelder* hosts workshops on repairing, maintenance, and upgrading, aimed at equipping people with the skills needed to embrace sustainable living practices. Recognizing the importance of community outreach, *Paranduskelder* collaborates with local influencers and utilizes diverse media channels to raise awareness about the environmental and economic benefits of repair.

Here are three most important factors to keep in mind when establishing something similar:

- **Community Engagement and Skilled Volunteers**
Building a strong volunteer base is critical. It's not only about having skilled individuals who can handle diverse repairs, but also fostering a supportive, inclusive environment where community members feel comfortable participating. Recruiting fixers who are enthusiastic about sharing skills and bringing in local partners—whether through schools, environmental groups, or municipal programs—can make a repair workshop truly thrive.
- **Accessible and Functional Venue**

Finding the right location plays a major role. It should be easily accessible to the community and have enough space for designated repair stations, seating, and a welcoming area for refreshments. A well-organized setup that encourages interaction between visitors and volunteers can transform a repair workshop into a community place rather than just a repair service.

- **Funding**

Initial funding is essential to cover basic tools for sewing, electronics, woodworking, etc. While community donations and grants (like *Paranduskelder*'s success with the Environmental Investment Centre) are great starting points, it's helpful to maintain a small budget for consumables and replacements. Setting up a donation jar during events or looking for sustainability-focused grants can ensure that the repair workshop has a steady supply of resources.

The investment can vary depending on factors such as location, size, equipment, and staffing needs. Setting up will be a one-time investment. *Paranduskelder* is a private initiative that collaborates with different stakeholders in EU projects focusing on sustainability and circular economy. They offer educational and training services to get income. The city of Tartu provides small financial support every year.

One of the biggest expense categories are human resources (ca 110 000 €/year, overall expenses totaling 147 500 €/year). The craftsmen are either volunteers or occupied with part-time employment. The next big expense is room rent (approximately 18 000 €/year), provided that the materials used for repairing are also second hand or repurposed materials. *Paranduskelder* brings in around 60 000 €. This is getting better every year, but still needs support through various projects.

Paranduskelder initially secured its funding through an environmental grant from the Environmental Investment Centre in Estonia. On April 23, 2019, they participated in the Negavatt energy-saving competition and were selected among the top 10 out of 77 entries. In the final round on May 28, *Paranduskelder* won second place, receiving a €5,000 startup grant. This funding was crucial for purchasing essential tools and equipment.

For others looking to start similar projects, exploring grants focused on environmental sustainability, circular economy initiatives, or community engagement can be beneficial. Platforms like local environmental investment centers, crowdfunding, and competitions focused on green initiatives can be valuable resources for initial funding.

4.4. ELiCo concept – The Recycling Master online course

4.4.1. The background

“ELiCo (Enlightened Consumer) concept utilizes both citizen engagement and possibilities available with digitalization. ELiCo develops CE thinking and practices of consumers in their everyday life. It aims to educate consumers in different areas of CE, especially in plastics, batteries and bio waste reduction and smart recycling.”

The goal was to produce content that supports and enhances the recycling competence of consumers belonging to special groups in plastic, battery, and organic waste recycling. Depending on the opportunities and agreements, other recycling themes that are deemed meaningful to the target audience and could fit into the overall implementation may also be addressed in the content.

The result of this Stakeholder engagement demo was Kierrätysmestari -online course (Recycling Master in English). The aim is that the content will be localised to Norway and Estonia too.

The overall budget for creating ELiCo concept was 50.000€, which 30.000€ for content creation and workshop facilitation and 20.000€ for translations and localisations. A budget for a digital learning platform should also be reserved, or an existing platform should be available. In Helsinki's case, the city's existing Moodle platform was used. In principle, Moodle is free, open-source software; however, technical expertise and understanding are required for its installation.

4.4.2. Preparation

To get the best and the most useful result of the work started with the two-step development Innovation Competition where in the first round was identification of needs and partners and then the second phase was an innovation competition for the content creators and subcontractors to develop the concept and the content. The aim was to find a committed partner who has the need and the will to maintain and develop material after the pilot.

- Phase I: Identify the need and the committed partner
Phase II: Call for the innovators/companies

The result of the ideation and partner search phase was to create the concept for “Recycling know-how for customers of Social Rehabilitation Services”. The work was decided to be done in cooperation with Rehabilitative Work Activities, and Disability Service Unit of the City of Helsinki. The focus of the work was to foster the civil skills for the customers and offer an online course which also would be available for self-study materials on Moodle platform they already had.

4.4.3. The focus groups

The concept concerns the design and implementation of educational materials aimed at strengthening recycling expertise. The materials are intended to teach the basics of recycling and their application as an everyday civic skill for clients in rehabilitative work activities and disability services work activities.

Rehabilitative work activities are intended for individuals who, due to limitations in their work and functional capacity, cannot participate in public employment services or work, with the aim of improving the client's life management and functional capacity. In the context of disability services work activities, the participants include adults with developmental disabilities and those on the neurodevelopmental spectrum, whose functional capacity and support needs vary significantly.

4.4.4. Desired requirements

When preparing materials for special learners you must take into account some features, like visuality, gamification, accessibility and plain language. As already mentioned, the suitability for self-study was a focal requirement. When talking about learning materials also the pedagogic approach was part of the planning process. In the case the narrative pedagogy and the Bloom's taxonomy were defined to guide the material production.

4.4.5. Replicability and localisation

One of the key elements of TREASoURcE project has been to develop methods or results which can be replicated in other countries or areas and explain the basic concept and share the lesson learned. The purpose of the localisation is to provide a wider benefit from the created materials.

The first version of ELiCo content was created in Finnish and by following local recycling instructions in Finland. Localisation for Norway and Estonia will be done after the Helsinki project is finished during Q1 2025. In addition to translations (Norwegian and Estonian), the localisation is needed to meet local recycling practices and regulations. Forum Virium Helsinki will host and keep Moodle environment available for the local implementations during the project.

4.4.6. Financing options for the course

There are various funding options and here are listed the potential funding options in Finland, Estonia and Norway. The list is based on general assumptions.

Funding options in Finland

Public funding and grants - look for funding opportunities that support sustainable development, the circular economy, or education:

- **ELY Centres** (Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment, 2024) **and Business Finland** (Business Finland, 2024): Offer funding for projects that promote the circular economy or education.
- **Ministry of Education and Culture** (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2024): Supports education and cultural projects.
- **EU Funding Programs**: Programs like Erasmus+ (Erasmus+, 2024) and (LIFE Programme, 2024) can fund education and environmental projects.
- **Sitra** (The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra, 2024): Focuses on the circular economy and often provides funding for related projects.
- **Local Governments**: Many municipalities support sustainability projects.

Foundations and funds - seek foundations that support sustainability or educational initiatives:

- **Jenny and Antti Wihuri Foundation** (Jenny and Antti Wihuri Foundation , 2024): Jenny and Antti Wihuri Foundation is a Finnish non-profit organization that supports hundreds of projects in the areas of research, art and societal activities every year.
- **Kone Foundation** (Kone Foundation, 2024): Kone Foundation awards grants for academic research, the arts, and for projects which combine scholarly and artistic approaches.
- **Maj and Tor Nessling Foundation** (Maj and Tor Nessling Foundation, 2024): Especially for projects related to the environment and sustainability.
- **Sitra's Circular Economy Fund** (if available)

Partnerships and sponsorships - consider collaborations with companies or other organizations:

- **Corporate Partnerships**: Many companies are eager to support circular economy and sustainability initiatives as part of their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).
- **Professional Associations and Organizations**: They might be interested in supporting if the course benefits their members.

Crowdfunding - utilize crowdfunding platforms:

- **Mesenaatti.me** (Mesenaatti.me, 2024): A popular crowdfunding platform in Finland

- **Kickstarter** (Kickstarter, 2024) or **Indiegogo** (Indiegogo, 2024): International crowdfunding alternatives
- Create an engaging campaign to attract people to support your project.

Other funding sources

- **Participatory Budgeting:** Some municipalities have programs where citizens can vote on projects to be funded.
- **In-kind Sponsorships:** Support may come in the form of technology, marketing, or other resources instead of direct funding.

Course monetisation opportunities

If the online course is partially paid, you can offer:

- **Freemium Model:** Basic course content is free, with additional materials available for a fee.
- **Partnerships with Educational Institutions:** This can help with marketing and reaching a broader audience.

Funding options in Estonia

Public grants and government programs

- **Environmental Investment Centre (KIK)** (Environmental Investment Centre, 2024): Provides grants for projects related to environmental protection, sustainability, and education.
- **Enterprise and Innovation Foundation (EIS)** (Enterprise Estonia, 2024): Offers funding for innovative projects, including those related to education and sustainability.
- **Estonian Ministry of Education and Research** (Estonian Ministry of Education and Research, 2024): Supports educational initiatives, especially those promoting lifelong learning and digital education.

EU funding opportunities

Estonia actively participates in EU funding programs:

- **Horizon Europe** (Horizon Europe, 2024): Supports research and innovation projects, including sustainability and education initiatives.
- **Erasmus+** (Erasmus+, 2024): Provides funding for educational and training projects with a focus on digital education and sustainability.
- **LIFE Program** (LIFE Programme, 2024) : Focuses on environmental and climate action projects.

Foundations and NGOs

- **Estonian Environmental Fund (Keskkonnafond)**: supports environmental projects in areas such as resource protection, biodiversity conservation, pollution reduction, and sustainable development. In Estonia, most environmental funding is managed and allocated through the Environmental Investment Centre (KIK) (Environmental Investment Centre, 2024).
- **Open Estonia Foundation** (Open Estonia Foundation, 2024): Supports projects focused on social change, including sustainability and education.
- **Nordic Council of Ministers' Programs** (Nordic Council of Ministers, 2024): Offers grants for Nordic-Baltic cooperation, which can be relevant for cross-border educational initiatives.

Corporate partnerships and crowdfunding

- **Local Corporate Sponsorships**: Estonian companies interested in CSR may sponsor circular economy projects.
- **Hooandja** (Hooandja, 2024): An Estonian crowdfunding platform similar to Kickstarter (Kickstarter, 2024), where you can raise funds for educational projects.

Funding options in Norway

Public grants and government support

- **Innovation Norway** (Innovation Norway, 2024): Provides funding for projects that promote innovation, sustainability, and education, including online courses.
- **Norwegian Environment Agency (Miljødirektoratet)** (Norwegian Environment Agency, 2024): Offers grants for projects related to climate action, sustainability, and environmental education.
- **Directorate for Higher Education and Skills (HK-dir)** (Norwegian Directorate for Higher Education and Skills, 2024): Supports educational projects, particularly those that involve innovative learning methods.

Nordic and EU funding programs

- **Nordic Council of Ministers Grants** (Nordic Council of Ministers, 2024): Supports Nordic cooperation in education and sustainability.
- **Erasmus+** (Erasmus+, 2024) **and Horizon Europe** (Horizon Europe, 2024): Available to Norwegian organizations despite Norway being outside the EU, with funding for digital education and sustainability projects.

Foundations and trusts

- **Sparebankstiftelsen DNB** (Sparebankstiftelsen DNB, 2024): Offers grants for community projects, including education and sustainability initiatives.
- **Gjensidigestiftelsen** (Gjensidigestiftelsen, 2024): Supports projects that benefit society, particularly those focused on education and the environment.
- **Norwegian Research Council** (Norwegian Research Council, 2024): Funds research and innovation projects, including those focused on sustainable development and education.

Corporate partnerships and crowdfunding

- **CSR programs from companies:** Many Norwegian companies have strong CSR initiatives that could align with a circular economy project.
- **Bidra.no** (Bidra.no, 2024): A Norwegian crowdfunding platform where you can raise funds for projects like online courses.

5. Key value chain demonstrations (KVC-demos) and replications, case examples

5.1. Plastics

5.1.1. Rigid plastics collection

The Tampere Region's recycling campaign for rigid plastic was a collaborative effort involving Ecofellows, Pirkanmaa Waste Management Company and TAMK (Tampere University of Applied Sciences) students. The project aimed to address the challenge of collecting and recycling rigid plastics, which don't yet have an efficient recycling system in Finland. Most of the rigid plastics waste and side streams are being incinerated at the moment. By conducting a composition study of rigid plastics collected from municipal and household sources, the project provided valuable data that can affect future waste management strategies (TREASoURcE, Rigid Plastic Composition Study, 2024).

The implementation of the demo revealed several possibilities but also challenges. The project successfully identified and categorized various types of rigid plastics, providing a clear picture of the waste composition in the region. However, the process was not without surprises. Weather conditions, such as snow, posed some challenges during the sorting process, affecting the accuracy of the data. These issues were mitigated by adapting the methodology, such as visual inspection and recycling symbols to categorize plastics. For replication, it is crucial to ensure adequate equipment and consider environmental factors that might impact the sorting process. Additionally, engaging local stakeholders and maintaining clear communication channels can enhance the project's success. It is also a challenge that rigid plastic

consists of various plastic and product types which of course set challenges for sorting and reuse/recycling of the materials. Rigid plastics collection campaign provided high quality feedstock for both mechanical and chemical recycling, especially when manual sorting was applied. This can be replicated with the help of municipalities for larger regional campaigns and engagement of pretreatment/sorting companies. The current achieved capacity can be scaled up for larger volumes that can meet industrial companies' operational capacity (TREASoURcE, Collection and Sorting Campaign, 2024).

To construct a roadmap for funding and investment, it is essential to leverage both public and private sources. Actually, other pilots were carried out alongside this demo in BT led KIERTOTRE project (KIERTOTRE, 2024), focusing on rigid plastics from private sector – the other one focusing on rigid plastics suitable for mechanical recycling and the other one on rigid plastics suitable for chemical recycling. It was of great importance that we could combine the results of both TREASoURcE and KIERTOTRE pilots to learn more about the rigid plastic types, compositions and amounts from both the municipal and private sectors.

Funding possibilities

Locally, initiatives can tap into regional development funds and national grants aimed at promoting circular economy practices. Engaging with i.e. Business Finland (Business Finland, 2024), the Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra (The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra, 2024) and Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment, 2024) can provide substantial support for research and development. On the private side, building strong business cases that highlight the economic and environmental benefits of recycling rigid plastics can attract venture capital and corporate investments. Establishing partnerships with large corporations committed to sustainability can also provide financial and logistical support. Creating pilot projects that demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of these initiatives can further strengthen the investment pipeline. It is also important to continuously foster local and regional key stakeholders in the value chain in order to boost further development.

For broader exploitation and implementation, the demo can serve as a model for other regions facing similar challenges with rigid plastic waste. Sharing the findings and methodologies through platforms like the TREASOURCE replication handbook can inspire other municipalities and waste management companies with their value chain partners to adopt similar practices. Additionally, fostering value chain development and international collaborations and participating in global networks focusing on circular economy can help disseminate best practices and innovations. By continuously refining the approach based on feedback and new developments, the model can be adapted to different contexts, promoting a more sustainable and circular economy on a larger scale.

5.1.2. Chemical recycling of plastics

Background info and ideas

The chemical recycling of plastics represents a rapidly growing and critical area for both the waste management and chemicals industries. Successful business development in this space requires navigating technological, regulatory, and market challenges. Securing funding is often complex, but both public and private investments are increasingly directed toward circular economy solutions, with chemical recycling as a core component. Developing a solid investment pipeline involves attracting early-stage capital, securing strategic partnerships, and proving the scalability and profitability of the technology. As governments and industries worldwide move toward stricter plastic waste reduction targets, chemical recycling stands to play a key role in creating a more sustainable future.

Ecobarge technology was originally developed for pyrolysis of plastic waste into energy (gas and oil). But testing will continue during classification of plastic waste feedstock to produce suitable quality pyrolysis oil by chemical recycling. The technology was installed as a modular unit which enables smoother transportation and replication potential for further exploitation activities. Scaling up the technology will be possible; this can limit the mobility of the installed plant, but there would be larger built-up capacity.

Chemical recycling of plastics: Business development, funding, and investment pipeline

Chemical recycling is gaining traction as an alternative to traditional mechanical recycling, offering a more scalable and efficient way to handle mixed and contaminated plastic waste. It involves breaking down plastics into their monomers or other valuable feedstocks, which can then be used to produce new plastic materials or other chemicals. This process can address the limitations of mechanical recycling, such as the inability to recycle complex plastic materials or the degradation of plastic quality over time. To successfully launch and scale chemical recycling ventures, businesses must navigate the following key areas: business development, funding, public and private investments, and building an investment pipeline.

Here's an overview of these components:

Business development for chemical recycling

The success of a chemical recycling business hinges on several factors:

A. Technology development and scaling

- **Technological feasibility:** The technology for chemical recycling is still evolving. Startups and established companies need to develop cost-effective and scalable processes. Key technologies include pyrolysis, gasification, solvolysis, and enzymatic degradation. Each process has its advantages, and selecting the right one depends on the type of plastic waste being processed.

- **Partnerships with research institutions:** Many chemical recycling companies collaborate with universities or research institutes to develop cutting-edge technologies. Engaging in R&D collaborations can de-risk technological uncertainties and accelerate innovation.

B. Supply chain development

- **Feedstock sourcing:** Access to a consistent and high-quality feedstock (plastic waste) is critical. Companies need to establish relationships with waste management companies, municipalities, and industries generating plastic waste. This could include sorting, cleaning, and preparing plastics for chemical recycling.
- **Recycling infrastructure:** Building or upgrading facilities for chemical recycling requires significant capital. Companies must plan for the construction of chemical recycling plants, or partner with existing facilities capable of handling the required processes.

C. Regulatory compliance and certifications

- Chemical recycling is subject to environmental regulations and approvals, which can vary by region. Companies need to understand the regulatory landscape and ensure compliance with environmental standards, safety protocols, and waste management practices.
- Obtaining certifications or partnering with industry leaders (e.g., in the plastics, automotive, or packaging sectors) can improve credibility and attract investment.

Funding for chemical recycling ventures

Chemical recycling projects are capital-intensive, often requiring both early-stage and long-term funding. The funding process typically involves a mix of private and public capital.

A. Early-stage funding

- **Seed funding & venture capital (VC):** Early-stage companies in chemical recycling can secure funding from angel investors, venture capital firms, or impact investors. Many investors are looking for innovative solutions to plastic pollution and are willing to fund startups with promising technologies.
- **Government grants and subsidies:** Many governments offer grants, tax incentives, or low-interest loans for projects that aim to reduce plastic waste, promote circular economy practices, or improve recycling technologies. These grants can come from local, regional, or national governments, particularly in Europe, the U.S., and Asia.

B. Growth and expansion stage funding

- **Private equity and strategic partnerships:** Once a chemical recycling company has proven its technology and achieved some commercial success, private equity investors and strategic partnerships with established players in the plastics, chemicals, or waste management industries may provide the capital needed for scaling. These investors often look for companies with a proven market fit and solid growth potential.

- **Debt financing:** Companies may also turn to debt financing, such as bank loans or green bonds, to fund infrastructure development or expand their operations. Green bonds, in particular, are gaining popularity as a way to finance environmentally sustainable initiatives.

Public and private investments in chemical recycling

The growth of chemical recycling is being driven by both public and private sector investments.

A. Public investments

- **Government programs & legislation:** Governments globally are increasingly recognizing the importance of chemical recycling in tackling plastic pollution. Initiatives like the European Union's Green Deal (European Green Deal, 2024) or national plastic waste reduction targets may offer funding opportunities, such as through specific environmental programs or clean technology funds.
- **Public-private partnerships (PPP):** Governments are also entering into partnerships with private companies to co-finance the development of recycling infrastructure or provide incentives for the establishment of chemical recycling plants.
- **Innovation challenges:** Public institutions often run innovation challenges or prize competitions to support breakthrough technologies in waste management and recycling. European Innovation Council (EIC) (European Innovation Council, 2024) have supported projects that promote recycling innovation.

B. Private Sector Investments

- **Corporate investment:** Major corporations in the plastics, packaging, and consumer goods industries are increasingly investing in chemical recycling technology, either through direct investment or partnerships.
- **Venture capital and corporate ventures:** Many large companies have established venture capital arms to invest in innovative startups, including those focused on recycling and sustainability. These investors provide not only capital but also strategic support, such as access to global supply chains or marketing channels.

Building an investment pipeline for chemical recycling

To build a robust investment pipeline, companies need to attract and maintain investor interest throughout the lifecycle of the project. This involves several steps:

A. Market research and risk assessment

- Investors need to understand the potential market size for chemical recycling and its scalability. Market research is critical in identifying regional opportunities, assessing the competitiveness of different technologies, and understanding regulatory trends.
- Risk assessment includes analysing technology risks, feedstock availability, market risks, and the potential for changing regulations that could impact the industry's growth.

B. Establishing a compelling business model

- **Revenue streams:** Chemical recycling companies can generate revenue through the sale of recycled plastics, intermediate chemicals, or byproducts. In addition to direct product sales, companies may explore licensing or partnership models with established companies in the plastics or chemicals industries.
- **Circular economy integration:** Investors are increasingly focused on businesses that align with the principles of the circular economy. By demonstrating that the company is part of a larger, sustainable ecosystem, chemical recycling companies can enhance their appeal to impact investors and ESG (environmental, social, governance)-focused funds.

C. Building a track record of success

- **Pilot projects:** Developing small-scale pilot projects or demonstration plants can serve as proof of concept and reduce investor uncertainty. These projects also help in refining the technology and establishing operational know-how.
- **Partnerships with industry leaders:** Forming strategic alliances with large companies in the plastics, chemical, or waste management sectors can provide credibility, facilitate access to capital, and reduce risks.

Key points on pyrolysis of plastics and feedstock quality

1. Feedstock quality and pyrolysis output

- **Pyrolysis temperature range (400-650°C):** At temperatures around 400-650°C, the pyrolysis process decomposes plastics into smaller hydrocarbons, which mainly produce oil (liquid and wax, gas, and char. The specific distribution of these products depends on the type and purity of the plastic waste fed into the system.
- **Heterogeneous feedstock:** One of the main challenges in chemical recycling of plastic waste is the complexity of its composition. Mixed plastic streams from municipal sectors typically contain mixtures of polyethylene, polypropylene, polystyrene, PET, and multilayer packaging. Polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) are the most common plastics in packaging and also the most desired feedstock for pyrolysis. The absence of any functional groups or heteroatoms in the polymeric structure make them ideal for the production of petrochemical intermediates. The product from thermal pyrolysis of PE and PP contains typically paraffinic compounds with a wide hydrocarbon distribution (liquid and waxes). Secondary upgrading of the pyrolysis oil from PP and PE might still be needed to produce suitable compounds for the petrochemical industry. Pyrolysis of polystyrene is also of great industrial interest due to its capability to produce styrene with very high yields. PET and PVC are on the other side not suitable for pyrolysis due to the high oxygen and chlorine content, which produce some undesired acids and toxic compounds.
- **Contaminated feedstock:** Another important aspect in the area of mixed plastic waste pyrolysis is the presence of contaminants and additives in the feed. For example, organic and paper and

cardboard derived contaminants may be present in real plastic wastes, which arise from labels, caps, lids, food residues, etc., introducing unwanted elements in the feeds. Additives are commonly added to polymers to enhance their properties and lifespan. The most common unwanted elements in these contaminants and additives are different metals (Ca, Al, Na, Zn, and Fe) and halogens (Cl, F). These heteroatoms may cause some corrosion of reactors caused by halogens and sulphur, deposition and coking in the reactor due to the presence of metals, and deactivation of catalyst in further refining of the pyrolysis oil.

2. Improving feedstock quality through sorting

- **Government-supported sorting systems:** A robust, government-backed waste collection and sorting infrastructure could make a significant difference in improving the quality of feedstock for pyrolysis. By separating plastics by type (e.g., PE, PP, polystyrene (PS) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET)) and removing contaminants (such as PVC, metals, or organic waste), you can ensure that the plastics sent to pyrolysis are more uniform and compatible with the desired outputs.
 - **Sorting technologies:** Advanced sorting technologies like near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, air classification, and automated shredding systems can play a role in streamlining the sorting process and ensuring that only suitable plastics are fed into the pyrolysis reactors.
 - **Cleaner waste streams:** If the waste management system prioritizes the collection of clean plastic waste, the resulting feedstock will be easier to process, improving yields and lowering operational costs. Cleaner plastic waste reduces the need for pre-treatment which can save time and money for pyrolysis operators.

3. Impact of contaminants on pyrolysis performance

- **PVC:** PVC is notorious for producing hydrochloric acid (HCl) when pyrolyzed, which can corrode equipment and produce harmful emissions. This is why the presence of PVC in the feedstock needs to be minimized. If there's no efficient sorting, the introduction of PVC will compromise the overall performance of the pyrolysis system, by the release of corrosive HCl and other toxic chlorinated hydrocarbons.
- **Other contaminants:** Food residues, paints, or coatings can introduce additional contamination, leading to decreased quality of the final products (especially oil). Metals, for instance, can create ash residues that reduce the efficiency of the pyrolysis reactor.
- **Moisture content:** High moisture content in plastic feedstock (often from food waste or poorly stored plastic) can negatively impact the pyrolysis process by requiring more energy to heat the materials, thereby reducing overall efficiency and increasing operational costs.

4. Optimizing pyrolysis for maximum yield

- **Feedstock pre-treatment:** A government-supported waste sorting system can be complemented with pre-treatment processes such as shredding, drying, and cleaning of plastic waste before it enters the pyrolysis system. Pre-treatment reduces moisture and contaminants, which improves the thermal cracking efficiency.
- **Optimization of pyrolysis conditions:** The pyrolysis process itself can be optimized depending on the quality and composition of the feedstock. The temperature range, residence time, and reactor pressure can all be adjusted to maximize the production of oil (especially liquid fuels) rather than waxes or char. However, the quality of the feedstock will always be a limiting factor.
- **Catalysts and additives:** Some pyrolysis technologies use catalysts to improve the conversion of plastics to higher-value products, such as higher-quality oils or chemicals. Government investment in research and development could facilitate the use of catalytic pyrolysis processes, improving yields and product quality even when the feedstock is mixed or contaminated.

5. Role of government support

- **Financial support and incentives:** Governments can play a crucial role by offering financial incentives for recycling companies that invest in advanced sorting and pyrolysis technologies. Support could come in the form of grants, tax credits, or subsidies for R&D, infrastructure development, or capital expenditures related to waste sorting systems and pyrolysis plants.
- **Legislation and standards:** Governments can also create favourable regulatory frameworks that encourage the sorting of plastics at the source, such as through Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes or mandates on recycling content. Setting standards for the quality of plastics entering recycling streams will improve feedstock quality and enhance the effectiveness of chemical recycling technologies like pyrolysis.
- **Public-private partnerships (PPP):** Governments could collaborate with private companies and recycling organizations to build centralized sorting and pyrolysis facilities, helping scale up the deployment of pyrolysis as a mainstream recycling solution. By incentivizing the creation of an integrated recycling ecosystem, governments could ensure a steady and high-quality supply of plastic feedstock for pyrolysis plants.

6. Long-term sustainability and economic impact

- **Waste-to-value economy:** If feedstock quality improves through better sorting, the pyrolysis process can more efficiently convert waste into valuable products like synthetic oil, which could be used as a replacement for petroleum-derived fuels. This contributes to the circular economy, reducing reliance on virgin plastics and lowering the carbon footprint of plastic production.
- **Market for pyrolysis products:** With high-quality feedstock, the oil produced by pyrolysis can be upgraded into useful products, such as fuels for transportation or chemicals for industrial use.

The commercial viability of these products improves with better feedstock, making pyrolysis a more attractive business model for investors.

Summary

The success of the pyrolysis process is closely tied to the quality of the feedstock, and this quality can be significantly improved with an organized and efficient waste sorting system. Government support for waste management and sorting infrastructure could help address the issue of contamination, ensuring that only the most suitable plastics are sent to pyrolysis, thus improving the yield of high-value products like oil and reducing the amount of undesirable byproducts such as char.

A well-developed waste sorting system, combined with advances in pyrolysis technology, could transform plastic recycling by making it more efficient, economical, and sustainable. Governments, private industry, and technology developers all have key roles to play in creating the necessary ecosystem for pyrolysis to achieve its full potential.

The quality of the plastic feedstock directly influences the yields and composition of the pyrolysis products—oil, gas, and solid residue (char). A well-organized and efficient waste sorting system is crucial for improving the overall quality of the feedstock, which in turn affects the pyrolysis process and its profitability.

5.1.3. Circulated fluidized bed

For plastic pyrolysis various reactor technologies including fluidized bed, rotary kiln, screw kiln, vacuum pyrolysis, melting vessels, plasma pyrolysis and microwave have been developed. Rotary kilns and fluidized beds are already in commercial use for plastic pyrolysis, while other technologies, such as plasma and microwave assisted pyrolysis are promising but still require considerable research and development. The advantages of pyrolysis in a fluidized bed reactor are the excellent heat and mass transfer and process in continuous mode. In fluidized bed reactors the residence time is typically very short, which results in fewer secondary reactions and side products. Another advantage of the fluidized bed is the possibility to use catalyst as heat transfer media in the reactor, a process known as catalytic pyrolysis. Using the proper catalyst can enhance the degradation of plastics and promote specific reaction pathways, leading to higher yields of the desired target products.

Our main goal in the TREASoURcE project is to demonstrate the feasibility of the catalytic pyrolysis of unrecycled plastic waste into valuable aromatic chemicals, including benzene, toluene and xylene (BTX). These aromatics are key chemical building blocks in the chemical industry and used in plastics, synthetic fibers, detergents, pharmaceuticals, paints and more. The work will be done at different scales to find the best catalyst candidate and optimize the reaction conditions for BTX production. Both model plastic mixtures and real plastic samples originating from industrial, household and agricultural sources will be used

to demonstrate the performance of the technology. After a successful demonstration at VTT, the technology is expected to be suitable for upscaling to TRL 7-8, 2-5 years after the project with more industrial feedstock.

5.1.4. MODIX technology pilot

In TREASOURCE project we focus on recycling plastic waste streams which are often rejected from established sorting and recycling operations due to for instance their bulky and fluffy nature, multi-material composition. The invented all-in-one modular shredder-mixer-extruder (MODIX) has capabilities for cost-effective and high-capacity conversion of waste plastics into extruded polymer filaments as (i) feedstock for mechanical recycling into value added plastics, (ii) offering a route for removal of volatiles and dehalogenation of contaminated feedstock, and (iii) feedstock for chemical recycling to produce hydrocarbon oils for production of virgin and value-added products. For instance, MODIX can provide molten plastic feedstock to pyrolysis reactor, which would enhance efficiency of pyrolysis by reducing electric consumption of pyrolysis reactor and residence time. The electric consumption of MODIX (currently at TRL 6) is 0.7 kWh/kg of mixed plastic waste as feedstock with 12 kg/h operational capacity. The MODIX technology can be further scaled up to TRL 7-8 after the project by the industrial stakeholders. Besides direct customer projects commissioned for VTT, the possible funding for local enterprises can be acquired for instance, through Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment, 2024), Business Finland (Business Finland, 2024) and Enterprise Finland (Enterprise Finland, 2025).

5.2. EV batteries

5.2.1. Battery room and investment

One of the challenges with using EV batteries as energy storage, is where to place it. A common mistake can be to focus on the investment cost of the battery system itself without considering the investment needed for it to function safely in the building. Depending on the building's layout and characteristics, this can be everything from a small matter to a big investment cost. In any case, it is important to consider this early in the process, to identify the best option and avoid late changes which can be very costly. There may be significant difference between retrofit battery rooms and building battery rooms in new buildings. For a new building it is possible to plan the location and size of room to fit the battery, design of ventilation system, extinguishing systems, using fire safe construction materials and have sufficient electrical connections. With this planned from the start, the additional investment related to the battery room, will be significantly smaller, and the installation time and operation of the battery system will also improve.

For retrofit battery rooms, the task depends on what is available, and because each building is a special case there may be a considerable cost related to getting the information on the state of what is available. Internet connections, electrical connections, ventilation and other considerations are typical modifications

needing to be done. Modifications and additions will add significant cost to the installation. Proper safety assessments of the installation and use of the battery must also be accounted for. This may include hiring consultants to perform these assessments.

In cases where the building does not have any suitable room to place the battery and the cost of retrofitting is too large, it may be considered to place the battery system in an outdoor container. An outdoor container which is not considered a part of the building, will reduce the consequence of a fire, and the need of permits and regulations associated with a possible fire hazard inside buildings. Still, a thorough fire safety and risk assessment must be done for the container.

While the use of batteries as energy storage in buildings is becoming increasingly common, it is still a relatively new concept. This means there generally still is a lack of government directives and standards for battery storage systems, and particularly for second life batteries. The consequence is a greater uncertainty around what to consider as safe, which often leads to hiring consultants. This adds cost and uncertainty compared to following a written standard.

Typical safety measures to consider in a battery room is:

- Fire resistant building materials.
- Battery room must be an isolated fire cell.
- Placement of room should be on ground-level, close to emergency exit and easy access from the outside.
- Sufficient weight capacity due to heavy batteries.
- An adapted ventilation, that does not mix with the overall ventilation, but has a direct outlet outside the building. In the case of a battery fire, toxic gases are released that should not be in the building's overall ventilation. In addition, it's important that these are removed from the battery room to avoid risk of explosion, which is the opposite to some ventilation systems that are designed to close the outlet in the case of fire.
- Room temperature should remain within reasonable levels for battery safety, e.g. 10-30°C. Room should be kept clean and dry.
- Room must have access control, only available to competent personnel.
- A safety disconnect switch in case of emergency.

5.2.2. Three demo sites

Second life EV batteries have been used as energy storage on three demo-sites: Rudskogen, Trosvik and Lempäälä. Two of these demo sites are in Norway (Rudskogen, Trosvik) and one in Finland (Lempäälä). Each case had different challenges and solutions with creating a suitable space for the batteries.

1. Trosvik

Trosvik is an elementary school located in Fredrikstad. The building has solar panel on the roof which can make a battery energy storage system particularly beneficial. The battery was installed here in a special room created for the battery system, placed inside an unused garage.

Battery room investment costs included:

- Built room from scratch with fire resistant building materials.
- Adapted ventilation
- Electrical connections
- Communication connections. 4G modem.
- Fire safety consultant
- Temperature control

Unexpected issues:

- Needed specialized solution for acceptable network safety

2. Rudskogen

Rudskogen is the national motorsports arena in Norway, located in Rakkestad. The motorsports arena has a consumption which is event based, with a low general consumption compared to the highest peaks, where the battery system can contribute and be very beneficial. The battery system was installed inside a container.

Battery room (container) investment costs included:

- Electrical connections
- Fire safety consultant
- Communication connections, needed fibre connection to container
- Container adaptation (Rudskogen already had an available container)
- Thermal management, heat pump

Unexpected issues:

- Internet firewall issues. The battery control system is dependent on internet connection to work as intended. This led to slow installation, and restricted control and flexibility.

3. Lempäälä House

Multi-purpose municipality owned building in Lempäälä has a public library, a restaurant, public offices, and other services. The building has solar panels on the roof, and varied use of building gives varied energy consumption, making energy storage potentially beneficial.

Battery room investment costs included:

- External electrical installer
- Fire and safety consultant
- Electrical connections
- Aerosol-based fire suppression system
- Thermal management, heat pump
- Protection device between battery system and grid

Unexpected issues:

- Internet firewall issues. The battery control system is dependent on internet connection to work as intended. This led to slow installation, and restricted control and flexibility.
- Frequent power outages. Special case where power remains off after the outage, and system needs manual restart.

5.2.3. Optimization of BESS utilization

Optimal usage of BESS for stationary applications

There are many ways in which one can make a profit from installing a battery energy storage system (BESS), but in this text we will divide into three main ways, namely peak shaving, grid services and time-shifting. We define time-shifting as when the battery is used to obtain lower electricity costs through optimizing with respect to the spot price, i.e., it shifts the electricity production or consumption to more beneficial times according to the spot price. Peak shaving is when the BESS is used to lower the power tariff, by discharging during peak electricity consumption. Grid services are, as the name implies, when the BESS is used to perform services for the grid, such as stabilizing the frequency of the grid. We will look into each of these three BESS use cases, and shed some light on both challenges and opportunities.

A simple form of **time-shifting** would be to do energy arbitrage with the grid. As an example, one can imagine charging the BESS when the spot price is 0.2 EUR/kWh, and discharging later to the grid when the price is 0.3 EUR/kWh. If we assume 5 % loss when charging, and 5 % loss when discharging it gives the following numbers: $0.2/0.95 = 0.211$ EUR cost charge 1 kWh into the battery, and $0.3*0.95 = 0.285$ EUR is what you get when you sell it back to the grid later. This gives a **profit of 7.4 cent** per kWh of BESS operating. However, there may be VAT which needs to be added when buying energy from the grid, and which you do not necessarily get refunded when discharging to the grid. In that case, the profitability of energy arbitrage is significantly reduced. In the case of 25% VAT:

$0.2*1.25/0.95 = 0.263$ EUR/kWh will then be the cost to charge one kWh.

And when you discharge, you still get paid 0.285 EUR/kWh. Giving a much smaller **profit of 0.022 EUR**, a whole 70% lower than the case with no VAT (Value Added Tax).

For the general case the following equation describes the profit for one charge discharge cycle for a BESS:

$$\text{Profit} = P_{\text{low}} \left(R \cdot \eta_d - \frac{1 + \text{VAT}}{\eta_c} \right)$$

Where P_{low} is the spot price when charging, R is the ratio between the price when charging and the price when discharging, (i.e., $R = 1.5$ means the discharge price is 50% higher than the charging price), VAT is any value added tax which is not refunded when discharging, and η_d and η_c are the discharging and charging efficiencies, respectively.

As expected, a large R is favorable for a profitable BESS use case. However, it is also worth noting that VAT and efficiency are crucial for profitability as well. For instance, if the combined efficiency is below 50%, as in hydrogen systems, then the ratio between the high and low price needs to be at least a factor of two for there to be any possibility to make a profit, even without VAT. As an example: it would be impossible to make any profit with a hydrogen system if the spot price only varies between 0.2 and 0.3 EUR/kWh.

There can be other ways to profitability if the BESS is connected to solar power, for instance by charging when the solar power produces energy and discharging later when prices may be higher. Compared to having a battery connected to the grid, we have the benefit of no extra VAT in this case, since one never buys electricity from the grid. This can make the case of solar energy storage more profitable than doing energy arbitrage with the grid alone.

It can be even more profitable with the case of solar energy and consumption at the same site. For instance, if you have a factory with solar panels installed, and the panels produce more energy than the factory consumes midday, you will typically sell that extra solar energy to the grid. However, if you have a battery, you can store that extra energy during midday and use it to cover your own consumption later in the day. Consumption that otherwise would require buying energy from the grid, with VAT. Thus, BESS becomes extra valuable for sites where the battery can increase the self-consumption of solar energy, because this reduces how much VAT needs to be paid. To illustrate this case with numbers: if the price is 0.2 EUR/kWh midday, and 0.3 EUR/kWh in the evening, then you will get 0.2 EUR paid for a solar kWh, but you need to pay 0.375 EUR (25% VAT) when buying the same kWh in the evening, giving you a net cost of **0.175 EUR**. However, with BESS in this case, you can time-shift solar energy to cover your own consumption in the evening, and a profit of **0.175 EUR will be achieved for each kWh that is shifted**, if losses are neglected. There are some technicalities for calculating the effect of the losses, but if they are assumed to be 5% at both charge and discharge, then the profit will be $0.175 - 0.05 \cdot 0.375 - 0.05 \cdot 0.2 = \mathbf{0.146 \text{ EUR per kWh of BESS used}}$.

Comparing these three cases, we see that the profitability for BESS varies on several factors in a complex manner. VAT for instance will decrease the profitability of BESS if you are solely doing energy arbitrage

with the grid. On the other hand, if you have overproduction of solar energy, VAT will make the case for time-shifting with BESS more profitable. High electricity prices with large variations throughout the day generally increases the profitability of BESS. High round trip efficiency also improves the profitability, but again in a complex manner. Numerical optimization is needed for each case to determine how profitable time-shifting with BESS will be, as it can vary greatly as the previous examples have shown.

Peak shaving is another way to make a profit with BESS. It is common that electricity consumers pay a given tariff depending on how large their largest power draw or energy consumption during any hour is. For example, it may be that you have to pay 10 EUR/kW for the highest kW you draw from the grid each month. Thus, if you can reduce the peak power you draw, i.e., shave away the peaks in your consumption by discharging a BESS, you can make a profit from getting lower power tariffs. As with time-shifting, there is however great variability in how easy it is to make a profit from peak shaving. As a general rule of thumb the broader the peak in energy consumption is, the harder it is to shave. For instance, if you draw 100 kW more than average for only one hour, well, then a BESS of 100 kWh can shave it (if it can discharge as fast as 1 C). However, if your peak consumption of 100 kW lasts for 5 hours, then a 500 kWh BESS is needed to shave it (neglecting the BESS discharge losses). For these two cases the reduction in power tariff will be the same, but you will need to buy a five times larger battery to get that reduction in the latter case.

Another key problem with peak shaving is that one does not necessarily know when the peak will occur. An industrial site might have the exact same operation of equipment every day, so that one always knows when and how large the peaks are, making peak shaving relatively easy. However, if you run a hotel for instance, it is nearly impossible to know exactly when the guests will use their water boilers, irons, or air conditioning. One may alleviate this with estimates for energy consumption for air conditioning or heating by checking the weather forecast and similar, but if you are in the beginning of a month, it will be hard to estimate the consumption peaks at the end of the month. However, since the power tariffs often depend on the highest power draw during a whole month (or during the whole year in some cases even!), one would still need to consider the whole month when peak shaving. For instance, peak shaving medium peaks in the beginning of May might prove futile if there comes a heat wave at the end of the month, which causes air condition driven huge peaks which one only partially shaves. Thus, while peak shaving can be equally or even more profitable than time-shifting, it is also typically more risky and harder to predict how profitable it will be in real-world operation. Spot prices are typically given 24 hours in advance, making short-term energy arbitrage quite low risk. There is still some risk, as time-shifting can be influenced by consumption and production, but the overall risk is much lower than for peak shaving in many cases. Operating the BESS wrongly with respect to peak shaving on only one day during a month may end up ruining the profitability for the entire month, while missing out on time-shifting one day will only affect that day, and not the rest of the days in that month.

A key question for BESS operation is how to balance time-shifting and peak-shaving. If you are lucky, it might be that your consumption peaks are timed at the same time as peaks in the spot price. In this case, the optimal strategy for peak shaving will be the same as the optimal strategy for time-shifting. However, optimizing a BESS for time-shifting and peak shaving can be challenging if you have a site where

consumption, spot price and solar production vary in “conflicting ways”. For instance, if the consumption peak is at the same time as the lowest spot prices, then optimizing for peak shaving would demand discharge, but optimizing for time-shifting would demand charging of the BESS.

Finding the optimal usage of a BESS connected to a site with both peak tariff, spot price and solar production can be challenging, but it is far from impossible. If one knows both the consumption, production and spot prices, then mathematically speaking one has a clearly defined optimization problem that we do have solid experience in solving at SINTEF. It is a fairly large problem, as one has to optimize the BESS for every hour during a month simultaneously if the power tariff is on a monthly basis, but it is still very much solvable. Most times there is only one solution to this optimization problem, even though there can be several equally good solutions theoretically speaking. However, if one takes into account the uncertainty in future production, consumption and spot prices, then the optimal solution strongly depends on predictions and risk aversion. The highest profit is most often achieved by combining both time-shifting and peak shaving, but when trying to do this there will be a risk of missing out, especially on the peak shaving, which again might yield worse results than solely going for time-shifting if one is unlucky. Thus, a risk averse BESS operator might want to focus on time-shifting, while a more risk tolerant BESS operator may wish to attempt to profit from peak shaving as well.

A third way to make a profit from BESS is by doing **grid services**. The most well-known type of grid service would likely be frequency services, where the BESS either discharges to or charges from the grid, in order to help the grid maintain a stable frequency. There are different types of frequency services, based on how long the battery should (dis)charge, and based on how much notice in advance is provided. Especially for fast frequency regulation, BESS can be very valuable due to their fast response time in the range of milliseconds. Li-ion BESS has such a fast response time that they can even provide a service called synthetic inertia, by delivering energy in such a short time, that it gives a similar effect as having a generator with mechanical inertia connected to the grid.

Another form of grid service is voltage regulation. Simplified it can be thought of as frequency services, just that instead of using the BESS to keep the frequency steady, it is used to keep the voltage where it should be. For instance, if you are far away from a transformer in the grid, there may be issues with keeping the voltage high enough. Or if there is a lot of solar fed into the grid, there may be issues with keeping the voltage low enough. In either case, a BESS can help keep the voltage at the desired place. However, for all these grid services there are often significant regulative barriers for access to the market for them. For instance, frequency services are typically something only big actors can participate in, and there are often regulations such as requiring at least 1 MW or similar before you can participate in the frequency service market. There are ways around this for smaller actors, such as having a bigger company (often called an aggregator) control your BESS together with many other BESSs, so that the bigger company can participate in the frequency market with a fleet of many small BESS. However, the aggregator would in this situation typically take a significant part of the profits from the frequency services, leaving less for the owner of the BESS.

As discussed this far, there are many ways to make a profit with BESS. Charging and discharging a battery to modify your consumption is something anyone can do, whether it is motivated by peak shaving or energy arbitrage. Discharging to grid may require some regulative approvals, but is not necessarily too challenging to obtain if one is already allowed to sell solar energy to grid. Participating in the frequency market, however, is probably the most challenging from a regulatory perspective, as there are strict rules for being allowed to participate in grid service markets.

It is important to note that these different ways to use BESS set different demands to the BESS. For instance, the most profit from fast frequency services is obtained by having BESS which can charge and discharge very quickly, i.e., have high C-rates. However, if the BESS is used to shave peaks which last for several hours, then a fast-charging rate is not necessary. On another note, high round trip efficiency can significantly improve the profits from energy arbitrage and time-shifting, but will have little impact on frequency services on the other hand. There is a wide range of batteries on the market today. Among the Li-ion batteries there are many different types of electrodes. And even for batteries with the same electrode materials, there is still the design of the battery cells greatly influencing the use case of the battery. Thus, a lot of BESS expertise is needed to find the right BESS for a given site and application. Or the other way around; a lot of expertise is needed to find the right use case for a BESS at a given site.

Last but not least, one should not forget about the environmental impact of BESS. There has been some focus on the emissions and challenges associated with BESS production. However, one should also focus on the positive impact of BESS. BESS used for grid services and peak shaving can help prevent upgrading the grid, which is often very expensive, both when it comes to direct costs and the environment, as building new power lines is both area and resource intensive. Furthermore, a significant amount of energy storage is needed for expanding the utilization of renewable energy. Operating a BESS which charges when solar production is high, will indirectly help flatten out the prices, and increase solar profitability while at the same time lowering electricity prices when the sun is not shining. So, for some people who are mainly environmentally motivated, installing BESS can be a sound idea even if it does not have positive financial profitability over its lifetime.

5.3. Biobased side streams

5.3.1. Marketplace for biobased side and waste streams – KiertoaSuomesta.fi

Large quantities of biobased side and waste streams are generated annually from primary production and from the food industry. In Finland in 2020, 20 Mt of agricultural side streams and food industry residues were produced which of only 0,3 Mt were utilized in biorefineries (Ravinnekierto 2030, 2024). The digital marketplace, KiertoaSuomesta.fi (KiertoaSuomesta.fi, 2023) was developed and published by the TREASoURcE project in summer 2023 to promote the use of these biobased side streams and to provide a platform where the supply and demand could meet. The marketplace is targeted towards actors from agriculture, forestry, food industry, processing industry, and municipalities. The aim is the creation of new business opportunities and the promotion of the use and recycling of biobased materials.

To ensure the continued development, operational stability, and scalability of the marketplace for biobased side streams, a robust investment pipeline and business development strategy are essential. The marketplace could incorporate various business models to ensure financial sustainability, including:

- **User registration fee:** Charging a one-time or recurring fee upon user registration to access the marketplace services.
- **Commission on transactions:** A percentage-based commission on transactions conducted within the marketplace. This would require an integrated payment system, which is currently not in place.
- **Advertising opportunities:** Providing external advertisers with paid advertising spaces on the marketplace platform to generate additional revenue.

These business models could support the marketplace's operational costs while promoting the circulation and value generation of biobased side-streams in line with the EU's circular economy goals. However, each model requires a critical mass of active users to operate effectively, making early-stage user acquisition vital for success. Experience from the existing marketplace underscores that user acquisition can be challenging and resource-intensive, especially in a relatively niche sector. Addressing these obstacles will require a well-prepared, targeted marketing strategy that actively engages potential users, raises awareness of circular economy benefits, and builds trust in the marketplace as a viable business tool.

The marketplace requires both initial and sustained funding to optimize its technology, user engagement, and overall functionality. To launch the marketplace, an initial investment of around €40,000 is needed for core technological development - coding and creating a user-friendly, secure platform. In addition to the setup costs, ongoing monthly operational expenses of approximately €450 to cover essential administration can be expected. Furthermore, personnel resources for platform design, continuous marketing efforts, and stakeholder communication are crucial and can cause additional costs. These costs could be covered through a well-functioning business model.

Funding the digital marketplace creation

On the EU level, the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) (Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, 2024) complements the broader Horizon Europe program by fostering cross-border collaborations focused on urban and regional circular economies. Additionally, the Just Transition Fund (JTF) (Just Transition Fund, 2024) aims to assist regions heavily reliant on non-sustainable practices to shift towards more circular, sustainable methods, potentially offering support for national and cross-border marketplaces alongside with LIFE (LIFE Programme, 2024), Horizon Europe (Horizon Europe, 2024), European Agriculture and Innovation Network (EIP-AGRI) (European Agriculture and Innovation Network, 2024), and Interreg (Interreg Europe, 2024). These programs add essential resources for developing, implementing, and scaling the marketplace to promote circularity in primary production across the EU.

For national funding options in Finland, ERDF (European Regional Development Fund, 2024) offers support for projects enhancing regional competitiveness and sustainability, which could be relevant for developing the marketplace infrastructure. Additionally, Centres for Economic Development, Transport, and

the Environment (Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment, 2024) provide funding specifically for regional business and environmental development. Sitra (The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra, 2024) offers financial backing for circular economy projects, particularly those enabling material reuse and resource efficiency. Business Finland (Business Finland, 2024) also provides grants and loans for sustainable innovations, particularly in technology and business development. The Rural Development Program (Rural Development Program, 2024) supports projects benefiting rural areas, such as promoting sustainable agriculture and related funding can be applied through the Centres for Economic Development, Transport, and the Environment.

In addition, by seeking private sector partners, particularly those interested in circular solutions or aligned with biobased industry needs, the marketplace could receive additional investments and technical support. Private contributions may also come in the form of partnerships with logistics providers or companies specializing in biowaste transformation. Finally, private foundations fund innovations aligned with environmental goals, making them valuable contributors for pilots advancing sustainable practices.

5.3.2. Local bioeconomy system models development in Tampere region

Ecofellows has worked for creating local bioeconomy models around biogas and recycled fertilizer production in Pirkanmaa (Tampere region). Many municipalities aim for carbon-neutral energy production, to which local biogas production can bring a solution. Biogas production can utilize side streams that are currently completely unused or for which no final disposal site can be found, such as for example sewage sludge, manure, and spoiled animal feed. Municipalities are often in a key position in promoting biogas investments in their region. They often own the wastewater treatment plants in their area, and on the other hand, they provide services to the agriculture. Municipalities can build biogas plants themselves or help local businesses or agriculture to form biogas cooperatives.

Ecofellows' work for creating local bioeconomy models has started by contacting municipalities in the Tampere region about their interest in working together on the topic. Deeper cooperation has been initiated with four municipalities. The aim is to find a suitable model for implementing local bioeconomy cooperatives in these municipalities. These cooperatives or limited companies will invest in local biogas plants using agricultural and forestry side streams, which will produce not only ecological biogas but also recycled fertilizers as a by-product.

The demos have started by local biomass surveys. These included all possible biomasses, but in practice the most common have been manure and other agricultural side streams and sewage sludge. After the preliminary investigation, the available biomasses, their location and the companies (or farms) that are interested in joining the energy community that builds the biogas plant are known.

Two of the partner municipalities decided to focus on a biogas plant using sewage sludge, and together with four other municipalities in the surrounding area, they applied for funding for planning the plant from the Ministry of the Environment (Ministry of Environment, 2024). Their planning will be completed in

autumn 2025. In these municipalities, it is hoped that biogas will provide renewable energy and electricity for the municipalities' own wastewater treatment plants, as well as for nearby industry.

The digestate residue from a biogas plant treating sewage sludge is somewhat problematic for fertilizer use, as it is human based waste and often not suitable as such for use as fertilizer in food production. The municipalities' own project will also explore new techniques for processing this digestate to make it more suitable for fertilizer use.

In a third municipality, manure and other agricultural side streams were found enough for an average size biogas plant and the development of a local bioeconomy model has progressed to the recruitment of actors and the planning of a business model and searching financing for a cooperative or limited company. The municipality has identified possible locations for the biogas plant. This municipality is also considering what measures are needed to create a local agroecological symbiosis. The municipality wishes to promote the local and organic food production and is endeavoring to do so in its procurement policy. The municipality itself does not want to be involved in the biogas company but otherwise supports it as far as possible. In this municipality, the sales channel for biogas could be the gas network located in the area. This would open up the sales channel throughout Europe.

In the fourth municipality, work for developing a local bioeconomy model is just in the early stages. As a result of the demos in these municipalities in Tampere region, the tasks that need to be done when developing local bioeconomy models and how to proceed in similar projects will be identified. In addition, potential financing models will be explored, both for the development of local bioeconomy models and for biogas plant investments.

Funding the local bioeconomy model development

The Finnish Ministry of the Environment's Raki programme (Raki Programme, 2012): The funded investments and research, development and innovation projects that utilise nutrient-rich biomass and side streams from municipalities and create the conditions for a profitable recycled feed market. Projects to promote energy efficiency and neutrality in urban wastewater treatment were also supported. Two TREASoURcE partner municipalities were able to apply for funding for their development project under the Raki programme, but the last opportunity to apply was in June 2024, so no such funding is available anymore.

The TREASoURcE project has been actively working with local Leader groups (Leader, 2024). The Leader approach is implemented by 52 Local Action Groups (LAGs) operating in all rural areas of Finland. The Leader approach means activities, advisory services and funding for specific areas. The aim is to strengthen and develop local communities and businesses and to increase the vitality of the area. The central idea behind Leader is to harness the skills, knowledge and activities of local people for community development. Leader groups help to develop the vitality of the area based on the ideas and needs of local people. The core idea behind the Leader approach is to develop the area together with local people. This

is done by funding local development projects and providing help and support at all stages of project implementation.

Local action groups mobilise, motivate, inform, train and assist project promoters. All advisory services are free of charge. Leader groups in the Tampere region can fund the development of a bioeconomy model for local farmers and small entrepreneurs. For example, the logistics and investment planning of a biogas plant can be carried out with the funding from the Leader groups. However, municipal wastewater companies are not eligible for Leader funding. Funding from the Leader groups is the same funding than The Rural Development Program (Rural Development Program, 2024) mentioned in chapter 5.3.1. but Leader funding is targeted for smaller, locally-based businesses and associations.

5.4. Cross-cutting: The role of sustainability assessments in building investment pipelines for circular economy projects

Sustainability assessments and life cycle assessments (LCA) are essential tools for guiding investments in circular economy projects. Since the circular economy projects aim to minimize waste and reduce adverse impacts of economic activities, the role of sustainability assessment is crucial for proving that these objectives are met. By systematically evaluating a project's environmental, social, and economic impacts, the sustainability assessment helps investors and public bodies make informed funding decisions. These insights are key to attracting both public and private funding and building the investment pipeline.

5.4.1. Public funding

Public funding, including grants, subsidies, and loans, often requires projects to demonstrate alignment with governmental sustainability goals and regulatory frameworks. This is especially true as many governments now integrate sustainability metrics into tendering and funding criteria. Sustainability assessments enable projects to showcase their contributions to these goals, such as reducing the carbon footprint. This compliance with the policy goals documented by a sustainability assessment (or a life cycle assessment) is vital for securing public funding.

5.4.2. Private funding

Private investors, particularly those focused on impact investing, seek projects that deliver measurable social or environmental returns in addition to financial gains. Sustainability assessments are particularly valuable here, as they provide data on environmental impacts, resource usage, and potential social benefits. By offering transparent and quantitative metrics of sustainability, these assessments help investors align with their environmental and social impact goals. This appeal to impact-focused investors can increase the project's chances of securing funding from private sources. Moreover, environmental sustainability of the project might appeal also to profit-driven investors if presented as a future competitive advantage, which positions the project as being able to meet foreseeable consumer demand for sustainable

product and complying with prospective environmental regulation. In addition, the outcome of the sustainability assessment that proves economic sustainability of the project represents a major incentive for all investors.

5.4.3. Sustainability assessment framework for informing investments

Conventional LCA is limited in assessing the broader economic and social impacts essential to circular economy projects and often relevant for potential investors. Therefore, the sustainability assessment carried out to support funding should go beyond the conventional LCA and take on a more comprehensive approach. More specifically, a sustainability assessment framework for informing investment decisions should incorporate environmental, economic and social dimensions while considering the context of the system that the project will be deployed within. It is also important to ensure that all the indicators relevant from the regulatory perspective and impact investor perspective are assessed with a sufficient confidence.

Typically, the most relevant indicators from the regulatory perspective are the ones related to climate change and biodiversity. However, it is important to assess also other potential environmental issues beyond the ones commonly talked about and explain the importance of such assessment to the involved investors. The sustainability assessment framework should ensure that the generated results are easy to understand also for non-experts. In addition to environmental impacts, economic performance is an important dimension of the circular economy projects seeking investment. The economic analysis should involve assessment of the costs associated with all value chain activities/ activities associated with the life cycle of the project. The methodology of life cycle costing (LCC) is a good fit for this purpose. The LCC facilitates an understanding of costs associated with each activity within the project over time. Hence, the outcome of LCC is suitable for the calculation of net present value and internal rate of return, indicators important for assessing the profitability of investment decisions.

5.4.4. Engaging stakeholders with the assessment results

The engagement of stakeholders with the results of the sustainability assessment is crucial, as it determines to what degree they will take these results into account during their decision making. In general, the results of the assessment should be communicated in the way that highlights the importance of opting for solutions that reduce negative impacts and create positive value, while being easy to understand for non-experts. Additionally, the confidence in the results of the sustainability assessment should be fostered among the stakeholders by clearly demonstrating how the uncertainty of the analysis is addressed. Inclusion of the scenario analysis might be a suitable approach to address this uncertainty, which generates results, interpretation of which is easily comprehensible.

5.4.5. A novel sustainability and circularity assessment framework developed in the TREASoURcE project

In the TREASoURcE project, the newly developed sustainability assessment framework applies system dynamics linked to (prospective) life cycle sustainability assessments (LCSA) and (dynamic) material flow analysis (MFA) within a tailored and holistic framework. The context-based and multi-dimensional nature of the approach allows for more holistic assessments, essentially allowing for suitable recommendations for effective circular economy solutions. It acts as a decision-making tool that helps stakeholders, such as policy makers or businesses, make good decisions regarding possible circular economy strategies. More information regarding the framework can be found in D7.2 “Report on core and extended framework for sustainability and CE of system solutions” of the TREASoURcE project (TREASoURcE, D7.2, 2024).

6. CONCLUSIONS AND SUMMARY

In this report, the diverse landscape of current European, national, regional and local funding possibilities related to CE initiatives, is touched upon. It is clear that the availability and continuity of versatile funding sources, ranging from EU programs and national grants to venture capital, private equity, and green bonds, is critical in implementing systemic CE solutions as well as ensuring their sustainability and growth. In addition to traditional financing, also innovative financing models such as public-private partnerships, crowdfunding, and investment readiness programs are essential tools for attracting a broad spectrum of investors and driving CE investments. All these models not only foster collaboration but also secure long-term investments, creating a feasible financial ecosystem for various types of CE initiatives.

Stakeholder engagement emerges as a cornerstone for building consistent investment pipelines. Proactive outreach activities to cultivate collaboration among public and private stakeholders is essential also for the key value chain CE solutions development and implementation. Successful case examples such as fix and repair shops, plastic CE innovations, battery storage solutions, local bioeconomy model development and market platforms are presented in the report. Addressing their replication potential, best practices and learnings in addition to possible financing and investment planning strategies, inspire also other regions to adopt similar practices. Life cycle assessments are seen as indispensable tools for showcasing the environmental, social, and economic benefits of CE projects. By offering transparent and quantitative metrics, LCAs play an essential role in attracting both public and private funding.

The report emphasizes the importance of replication and scalability and by providing concrete examples and guidelines, a broader adoption of CE practices across various regions related to the addressed value chains may be achieved. It offers a set of practical insights, strategic guidance, and concrete examples, all designed to facilitate replication, investments planning and resilient investment pipeline building. The overall purpose is to enhance the visibility of the best practices and learnings from the TREASoURcE demos and replications and engaging stakeholders, reflecting on potential investment and financing possibilities to support the transition towards systemic circular economy solutions.

7. REFERENCES

- Baltic Sea Action Group.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.bsag.fi/en> 15.11.2024
- Beyond Circularity.* (2022). Retrieved from <https://www.valmet.com/about-us/about/research-and-development/beyond-circularity/> 18.12.2024
- Bidra.no.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://bidra.no/innsamling> 18.12.2024
- Bionova.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://arsrapport.innovasjon Norge.no/2022/en/artikkel/bionova-skal-hjelpe-norge-med-a-na-klimamalet> 16.12.2024
- Business Finland.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.businessfinland.fi/en/for-finnish-customers/home> 28.10.2024
- Case Fredrikstad | Fix and Repair Workshops in “Culture Night” Event.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://handbook.treasure.eu/case-fredrikstad-fix-and-repair-workshop-at-culture-night/> 20.1.2025
- CE Green Deal Commitments.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://sitoumus2050.fi/kiertotalouden-green-deal-sitoumukset#/?commitmentType=871646&category=kiertotalouden-green-deal> 18.12.2024
- Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.ely-keskus.fi/web/ely-en> 16.12.2024
- Circular Cities and Regions Initiative.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/> 15.11.2024
- Circular City Centre C3.* (2021). Retrieved from <https://advisory.eib.org/about/circular-city-centre.htm#guidance> 15.11.2024
- Circular City Funding Guide.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.circularcityfundingguide.eu/> 13.12.2024
- Cohesion Fund.* (2024). Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/cohesion-fund-cf_en 13.12.2024
- Council of Tampere Region.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.pirkanmaa.fi/en/> 15.11.2024
- EIC Investor Readiness and Outreach Programme.* (2024). Retrieved from https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-investor-readiness-and-outreach-programme_en 18.12.2024
- EIT InnoEnergy.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.innoenergy.com/>
- Energy Aid.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.businessfinland.fi/en/for-finnish-customers/services/funding/energy-aid> 16.12.2024
- Energy and Investment Aid.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://tem.fi/en/energy-support> 16.12.2024
- Enova.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.enova.no/> 15.11.2024
- Enova.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.enova.no/> 15.11.2024
- Enterprise Estonia.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://eis.ee/en/> 15.11.2024
- Enterprise Finland.* (2025). Retrieved from <https://www.suomi.fi/company> 20.1.2025

- Environmental Investment Centre.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://kik.ee/en> 15.11.2024
- EORI Number Registration Service.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://tulli.fi/en/businesses/services-for-businesses/e-services/eori> 16.12.2024
- Erasmus+.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/fi> 15.11.2024
- Estonian Ministry of Education and Research.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.hm.ee/en> 18.12.2024
- ETAg.* (2025). Retrieved from <https://etag.ee/> 20.1.2025
- EU Battery Regulation.* (2023). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/1542/oj> 15.11.2024
- European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development.* (2024). Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/european-agricultural-fund-rural-development-eafrd_en 13.12.2024
- European Agriculture and Innovation Network .* (2024). Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/node.html> 15.11.2024
- European City Facility.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.eucityfacility.eu/> 19.12.2024
- European Green Deal.* (2024). Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en 15.11.2024
- European Innovation Council.* (2024). Retrieved from https://eic.ec.europa.eu/index_en 18.12.2024
- European Institute of Innovation & Technology.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://eit.europa.eu/> 13.12.2024
- European Investment Bank.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.eib.org/en/> 13.12.2024
- European Regional Development Fund.* (2024). Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en 13.12.2024
- European Social Fund Plus.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://european-social-fund-plus.ec.europa.eu/en> 13.12.2024
- European Structural and Investment Funds.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.circularcityfundingguide.eu/funding-types-and-their-applicability/grants-and-subsidies/european-structural-investment-funds/> 13.12.2024
- FICompass.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.fi-compass.eu/> 19.12.2024
- Fingrid.* (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.fingrid.fi/en/pages/investors/financing/green-financing/green-bonds-framework/> 18.12.2024
- Finnvera.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.finnvera.fi/eng> 13.12.2024
- Gjensidigestiftelsen.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.gjensidigestiftelsen.no/> 16.12.2024
- Gjensidigestiftelsen.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.gjensidigestiftelsen.no/> 18.12.2024
- Green Transition Partnerships.* (2024). Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/whats-new/newsroom/14-11-2024-cohesion-policy-eur83-million-call-for-green-transition-projects-presented-at-un-climate-change-conference-cop29_en 18.12.2024
- Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://uudenmaanliitto.fi/en/> 15.11.2024

- Hooandja.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.hooandja.ee/en> 18.12.2024
- Horizon Europe.* (2024). Retrieved from https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en 13.12.2024
- How to Set up a Fix and Repair Workshop in a Cultural Event.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://handbook.treasure.eu/how-to-set-up-a-fix-and-repair-workshop-in-a-cultural-event/20.1.2025>
- Indiegogo.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.indiegogo.com/> 15.11.2024
- Innovation Norway.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://en.innovasjon Norge.no/> 15.11.2024
- Innovestor.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://innovestorgroup.com/> 18.12.2024
- Interreg Europe.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.interregeurope.eu/> 13.12.2024
- InvestEU.* (2024). Retrieved from https://investeu.europa.eu/investeu-programme/investeu-portal_en 19.12.2024
- JASPERS.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://jaspers.eib.org/> 19.12.2024
- Jenny and Antti Wihuri Foundation .* (2024). Retrieved from <https://wihurinrahasto.fi/?lang=en> 15.11.2024
- Joint Initiative on Circular Economy.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2024-151-the-joint-initiative-on-circular-economy-jice-steps-up-its-commitment-to-provide-eur16-billion-to-circular-projects-by-2025-and-welcomes-invest-nl-as-new-member> 13.12.2024
- Just Transition Fund.* (2024). Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/just-transition-fund_en 15.11.2024
- Kickstarter.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.kickstarter.com/> 15.11.2024
- Kiertoasumesta.fi.* (2023). Retrieved from <https://www.kiertoasumesta.fi/en/kiertoa-suomesta-english/> 15.11.2024
- KIERTOTRE.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://businessstampere.com/fi/tietoa-meista/hankekuvaukset/kiertotre/> 15.11.2024
- Kone Foundation.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://koneensaatio.fi/en/> 15.11.2024
- Korona Invest.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://koronainvest.fi/en/frontpage/> 18.12.2024
- KredEx.* (2025). Retrieved from <https://kredex.ee/et> 20.1.2025
- Leader.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://leadersuomi.fi/leader-ryhmat> 15.11.2024
- LIFE Programme.* (2024). Retrieved from https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life_en 13.12.2024
- Maj and Tor Nessling Foundation.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://nessling.fi/en/> 15.11.2024
- Mesenaatti.me.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://mesenaatti.me/en/> 15.11.2024
- Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://mmm.fi/en/frontpage> 5.12.2024
- Ministry of Economic Affairs and Development.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://tem.fi/en/frontpage> 5.12.2024

- Ministry of Education and Culture.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://okm.fi/en/frontpage> 15.11.2024
- Ministry of Environment.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://ym.fi/en/front-page> 5.12.2024
- Nordic Council of Ministers.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.norden.org/en/nordic-council-ministers> 18.12.2024
- Norwegian Directorate for Higher Education and Skills.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://hkdir.no/en> 18.12.2024
- Norwegian Environment Agency.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.environmentagency.no/> 18.12.2024
- Norwegian Research Council.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.forskingsradet.no/en/> 18.12.2024
- Open Estonia Foundation.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://oef.org.ee/en> 18.12.2024
- Ostfold.* (2025). Retrieved from <https://ofk.no/tjenester/tilskudd-og-stotte/kultur/tilskudd-til-festivaler-i-ostfold.186900.aspx> 20.1.2025
- Paranduskelder.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://paranda.ee/en/> 15.11.2024
- PRIA.* (2025). Retrieved from <https://www.pria.ee/toetused> 20.1.2025
- Raki Programme.* (2012). Retrieved from <https://ym.fi/en/project?tunnus=YM032:00/2023> 15.11.2024
- Ravinnekierto 2030.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://ravinnekierto2030.fi/> 15.11.2024
- Regionale Forskningsfond.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.regionaleforskningsfond.no/> 15.11.2024
- Repair Cafes.* (2017). Retrieved from <https://paranda.ee/en/repair-cafe/> 15.11.2024
- Research Council of Finland.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.aka.fi/en/> 28.10.2024
- Research Council of Norway.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.forskingsradet.no/en/> 15.11.2024
- RTK.* (2025). Retrieved from www.rtk.ee 20.1.2025
- Rural Development Program.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.ely-keskus.fi/maaseudun-yritysrahoitus> 15.11.2024
- Scalable Cities.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/scalable-cities> 19.12.2024
- Smart and Clean.* (2016). Retrieved from <https://smartclean.fi/> 18.12.2024
- Smart Cities Marketplace.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/> 19.12.2024
- Sparebankstiftelsen.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://sparebankstiftelsen.no/> 16.12.2024
- Sparebankstiftelsen DNB.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://sparebankstiftelsen.no/en/> 18.12.2024
- Superhealthy Buildings Ecosystem.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.kiilto.com/super-healthy-buildings-ecosystem/>
- Taaleri.* (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.taaleri.com/en> 18.12.2024

Tallinn City Government Grants. (2025). Retrieved from <https://www.tallinn.ee/et/tallinna-toetused> 20.1.2025

Tartu City Government Grants. (2025). Retrieved from <https://www.tartu.ee/et/toetused> 20.1.2025

Tesi. (2024). Retrieved from <https://tesi.fi/en/> 16.12.2024

The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra. (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.sitra.fi/en/> 5.12.2024

TREASoURcE. (2023). *D1.4 State-of-the-art analysis of technologies, circular business models and ecodesign practices for plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based side and waste streams.* <https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/TREASoURcE-D1.4-State-of-the-art-analysis-of-technologies-circular-business-models-ecodesign-and-good-practices.pdf>.

TREASoURcE. (2023). *D4.1 Existing and upcoming challenges for extending electric vehicle battery lifetime.* <https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/TREASoURcE-D4.1-Report-on-existing-and-upcoming-challenges-for-2nd-life-battery-use.pdf>.

TREASoURcE. (2024). *Collection and Sorting Campaign.* https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/TREASOURCE_Rigid_Plastic_Campaign_Collection_Sorting_11012024.pdf.

TREASoURcE. (2024). *D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains.* <https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/TREASoURcE-D1.3-Legislative-and-regulatory-framework-for-target-value-chains.pdf>.

TREASoURcE. (2024). *D7.2. Report on core and extended framework for sustainability and CE of system solutions.*

TREASoURcE. (2024). *Rigid Plastic Composition Study.* https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/TREASOURCE_TAMK_Report_Rigid_plastic_composition_study.pdf.

Tukes - Electrical Works in Finland. (2024). Retrieved from <https://tukes.fi/en/electricity/electrical-works-in-finland> 16.12.2024

Urbact. (2024). Retrieved from <https://urbact.eu/> 19.12.2024

Young Entrepreneurship. (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.ue.no/> 15.11.2024